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Abstract:	This document monitors, analyses, and evaluates all communication and dissemination activities during the second project year of PLATOON (M13-M24), developed as per the communication and dissemination strategy. The main outcome of this deliverable is that the majority of the communication & dissemination KPIs have been achieved, thus WP9 progressed very well during the second project year, and continues being ahead of the schedule.
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Terms and abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DM	Dissemination Manager
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	European Commission
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
EUSEW2020	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2020
GA	Grant Agreement
GAM	General Assembly Meeting
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LI	LinkedIn
PM	Project Manager
PU	Public
QA	Quality Assurance
Q&A	Question & Answer
RE	Restricted
REN	Renewable Energy
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SoMe	Social Media
TM	Technical Manager
TSO	Transmission System Operator
TTP	Tech Transfer Programme
TW	Twitter
VP	Vice President
WP	Work Package

WPL	Work Package Leader
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

The H2020 PLATOON project (“Digital PLatform and analytics TOols for eNergy”) is an EU-financed project that aims to digitalise the energy sector. PLATOON was launched in January 2020 (M1) and runs until December 2022 (M36). It will research ways to digitalise the energy sector by developing COSMAG-compliant reference architecture for big data processing. The project partners will create a digital platform and multiple analytics tools – specifically for the energy sector – that will gather and summarise information from multiple sources (i.e. renewable energy power plants, ESCOs, end users, TSOs, DSOs, etc.), thus helping stakeholders to find and use effectively the most relevant and updated information when being active on the energy market.

The “D9.4 Communication and Dissemination Report II” is a deliverable of WP9 “Communication and Dissemination” to be delivered in Month 24 (M24). The aim of this deliverable is to provide an insightful report about the communication and dissemination activities of PLATOON during the second project year as well as the targets and milestones that have been reached within the given time frame. PLATOON followed a widespread set of dissemination and communication activities in order to communicate the project outcomes to the public, stakeholders, potential users, and experts from the energy industry among others.

Chapter 1 briefly introduces PLATOON and the communication activities that have been made within the second project year. Chapter 2 gives a brief overview of the communication and dissemination strategy, namely the objectives that have been set at the start of the project, the specific target groups as well as the communication and dissemination channels and that have been used to reach various stakeholders. In Chapter 3 there is a detailed monitoring and analysis of the communication and dissemination activities on the website and social media channels, communication and dissemination campaigns, events, open calls, workshops and training, scientific publications as well as industrial dissemination.

Chapter 4 elaborates on the BRIDGE events in which the PLATOON partners took part. Chapter 5 concludes the most important outcomes of the deliverable as well as an outlook for the upcoming two project years. In Chapter 6, two companies give an internal review about this deliverable. And finally, in Chapter 7, we include some project-related references.

1. Introduction

The aim of “D9.4 Communication & Dissemination Report II” is to report the progress of PLATOON’s “WP9 Communication & Dissemination” during the second project year 2021

(M13-M24) to the European Commission (EC). D9.4 is due in December 2021 (M24). D9.4 monitors the overall success of all Communication & Dissemination activities for the second project year. The Knowledge and Tech Transfer Department of the Technische Informationsbibliothek Hannover (TIB-KTT)¹ is in charge of **T9.1¹ and T9.4 of the WP9 Communication & Dissemination** in the scope of the H2020 PLATOON Project.

Overall, it can be stated that WP9's success in the first project year could be continued in the second project year of PLATOON. The Twitter (TW) and LinkedIn (LI) accounts of the PLATOON project continued to grow steadily, as of 13 December 2021 (TW: **1020**; LI: **1770**). This means that the accumulated follower number of both TW and LI accounts is now **over 2700**. The PLATOON Partners have visited 28 online and offline events in M13-M24². This means that during the first two project years, **60 online and offline events** have been visited in total. On top of that, another KPI set in the PLATOON GA was already achieved in the second year of the project: **8 PLATOON Press Releases** were published on the project website and were disseminated on the Twitter and LinkedIn project accounts.

Thus, WP9 continues to be ahead of the schedule during the second project year of PLATOON.

2. Overview of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Objectives

The goal of WP9 Communication & Dissemination is to organise and execute measures to disseminate and communicate the project and the results it will deliver according to the dissemination and communication strategies, defined in D9.1; all with strict alignment to the project IPR principles.

The main objectives of WP9 (Task 9.1 and Task 9.4) are:

- Facilitate sharing of knowledge with external, targeted audiences, as well as towards other units of the consortium partners, get feedback from those audiences, and engage them with the project through targeted dissemination activities e.g. presenting at academic and industrial conferences, holding workshops and meetings with developers and engineers, etc.
- Promote visibility of the project and raise awareness about the topics it addresses through effective communication and outreach activities, e.g. publications, the maintenance of the project website, the distribution of printed and electronic material, publication of press releases, etc. The communication and dissemination strategy has been defined in D9.1 in greater detail. It will be refined and continuously improved at both individual-partner and consortium level. The success of the communication and dissemination strategy must be monitored in M12, M24 and M36 (D9.3).

¹ Task 9.1 of the PLATOON project has been finalized in M12, as per the GA.

² Out of the 28 events, TIB-KTT has visited 21 events.

2.2 Target Groups

Table 1: PLATOON Stakeholder Target Groups

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	BRIEF DESCRIPTION	WHY IS PLATOON INTERESTING TO THEM?	HOW TO ADDRESS THEM
PLATOON Consortium partners	All 20 partners directly involved in the PLATOON project. Wide range of institutions: enterprises, research institutes, public institutions, etc.	PLATOON is of crucial importance to all Consortium partners as it aligns fully with their organisational goals and strategic direction in the domains of digitalisation and the energy sector in particular	Social Media: YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn (YT, TW, LI), Printed Media, Newsletters, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Website, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform
Energy generation companies/ Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)/ Renewable Energy (REN) Companies	Commercial enterprises that focus on generating electricity, heat, hot water etc., as well as energy services to businesses and private households. Also focus on companies that specialise in renewable energy, green electricity trading and e-mobility.	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data. Operation and maintenance of REN power plants, as well as electricity grids can be improved (e.g. easier to foresee upcoming maintenance work, optimised grids thus longer lifespan of those). The project aims to increase the RE share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created which is especially good for start-ups and companies with innovative business models.	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform
TSOs/	Transmission System Operators and Distribution	Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, Newsletters,

DSOs	System Operators that operate and maintain electricity and gas grids; those who provide whole local areas or municipalities with energy.	expertise in Big Data.	Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform
Small and medium enterprises (SMEs)	<p>Small and medium-sized companies that focus on a business that is very closely linked to the energy sector; e.g. energy-heavy industries such as the automotive sector, mechanical engineering sector, pharma sector, construction sector etc.</p> <p>Especially those companies that have innovative and future-oriented business models.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>The project aims to increase the REN share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created, and this could be a chance for industries that could provide these with services, goods, know-how etc.</p>	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed Media, Live Sessions, Trainings, Workshops, Video Tutorials, Podcasts, PLATOON community on FBA platform
Energy End Users/ Building owners	Businesses and private households that consume energy. Also, those households/ businesses in focus that possess a REN plant in their homes, or those who want to buy	<p>Easier access to cheaper, more digitised and sustainable energy.</p> <p>A more decentralised energy system can be created that lowers costs for the energy users and interconnects households with each other (esp. via smart grids); energy security</p>	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Printed Media, Specific Communication Campaigns, PLATOON community on FBA platform

	eco power.	could be improved. Increased energy efficiency for buildings, offices etc. leading to significant cost savings.	
EU	Political instances of the EC that represent the interests of the European Union.	Increasing the REN share to reach the ambitious 2050 emissions goals. Help to create an inter-European energy grid that is better interconnected and much less dependent on fossil fuels (thus energy supply security on EU-level could be increased).	Newsletters, Social Media (TW, LI, YT), Specific Communication Campaigns
Municipalities	Cities, settlements or communes that are responsible for certain local/ national/ European areas.	Energy efficiency, optimised energy asset management and social welfare are key priorities of all municipalities and policy makers. Moreover, PLATOON addresses other topics such as smart cities, which are highly relevant	Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Press releases, Newsletter and Project Communication Material
Universities and Research centres	Public and private research and educational institutions that focus on providing people with constantly improving and up-to-date knowledge.	The project results/ milestone results are an important input that could enable universities and research centres to exchange knowledge, technology, data etc. and provide other stakeholders with valuable information (f.e. other scientific institutes, companies, etc.).	Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Journals, Specific Communication Campaigns, Printed media, PLATOON community on FBA platform
General public	All private persons that are generally interested in	The general public, i.e. private persons could be potentially interested in up-to-date energy	Fairs, Social Media (esp. TW, YT), General Communication Campaigns,

	energy, REN, data science, ecology etc.	<p>related topics such as REN, climate change, energy supply security, smart grids, and smart cities a.o.</p> <p>PLATOON addresses the interests of the general public due to the broad range of the topics that the project deals with. Thus, it can engage citizens who are not directly linked to the energy sector to engage themselves into energy topics and become proactive.</p>	Printed Media
Funding agencies	Commercial enterprises and public institutions (f.e. Economic development companies) that are providing start-ups, SMEs and projects on EU level with know-how and financial resources.	<p>Funding agencies focus on state-of-the-art developments in their sector.</p> <p>PLATOON being an innovative project funded by the EC, will make sure to communicate its output to funding agencies in relevant domains.</p>	Fairs/ Exhibitions, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Specific Communication Campaigns, Live Sessions, Workshops, Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform
Technological Platforms & Professional Associations and Initiatives	Public platforms that focus on technology-based topics such as Big Data, data Science etc. Example: Leibniz-Gemeinschaft.	PLATOON implements the digitalisation of the energy sector. Its use cases and pilots are highly relevant to related platforms and associations in terms of technology transfer, state of the art and lessons learned which can spur further synergies.	Journals, Social Media (YT, LI, TW), Website, Newsletters, Live Sessions ⁴ , Workshops, Trainings, PLATOON community on FBA platform

2.3 Communication Channels and Tools

2.3.1 Website and Social Media

Both the website and the social media channels are the main dissemination tools of the PLATOON project.

The PLATOON website is a cross-cutting online channel which hosts key information, e.g. press releases, blog posts, interviews, a brief project description, a page dedicated to the pilots of PLATOON, an introduction of each PLATOON consortium partner among others.

Social Media (SoMe) channels such as Twitter³, LinkedIn⁴ or YouTube⁵ are used to share experience and participate in conversations about the progress of the project and disseminate project results and outcomes. Here, a simpler language is used in order to attract people who are less familiar with energy-related or technical topics. Moreover, SoMe such as Twitter and LinkedIn were used to redirect visitors to the website. Also, a PLATOON YouTube channel has been created to disseminate video material of the H2020 energy project.

During the first two project years, the PLATOON LinkedIn account generated over **1700** followers, while the PLATOON Twitter account crossed the **1000**-followers-mark.

2.3.2 Online & Offline Events

During the second year of PLATOON, the consortium members visited a broad range of energy events or similar energy-related, technology, sustainability, ecology, business or climate events. The online events offered an excellent opportunity to participate in relevant energy-related events without being physically present in the event. During these online events, the TIB-KTT department made a great networking effort, i.e. connecting with relevant stakeholders and encouraging them to follow PLATOON on SoMe, just as during the first year of the project.

All the visited online and offline events had the focus on the energy sector and were mostly attended by technical stakeholders. However, there were also events on sustainability in a broader sense as well as on digitalisation and technologies related to the digital transformation. These events attracted stakeholders from NGOs, ecological institutions, EU institutions with focus on sustainability as well as ICT companies, technology providers, start-ups and accelerators, among others.

In total, the PLATOON partners visited **28 events**⁶, both offline and online, from M13 to M24.

³ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/platoon-h2020/>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWK6cuUlKW53Ap26OggXTvA/about>

⁶ Out of the 28 visited events from M13-M24, TIB-KTT has visited 21 events.

3. Communication and Dissemination Analysis & Results Monitoring

3.1 Website

The official PLATOON website of the H2020 PLATOON project has been designed to disseminate the project mission, vision, milestones & further info about the project. The structure of the website has been presented in D9.3. Further below are some major updates concerning the PLATOON Website.

- The page “Publications” has been added into the top menu bar.
- The subpage “Mentoring Committee” has been added to the “Network” page.
- The subpages “Supportive Partners”, “Accelerated SMEs & Start-Ups”, “Ambassadors Network”, “Tech Transfer Programme”, and “Mentoring Committee” have been constantly updated.
- The “Open Calls” page has been actively used to promote the 1st and 2nd PLATOON Open Calls
- The subpages “News & Events”, “Press Releases”, and “Interviews” have been actively used to promote the Interviews Campaign, the 6 latest press releases⁷, and the blog posts addressing the online and offline energy events and fairs.

3.1.1 Website Monitoring

Below in Table 2 is an overview of the most important website KPIs for the period M1-M24. Overall, over 12,800 visits (out of which almost 9,000 were unique visitors) have been achieved in the last 2 project years. The PLATOON website has been viewed over 46,000 times (and received almost 32,000 unique page views). Moreover, 30 blog posts, 12 different interviews with the members of the PLATOON consortium as well as 8 press releases (overall, there were 32 translated press releases). In a nutshell, the PLATOON website has reached a broad audience during the last 2 project years, and the number of visitors and page views is about to grow rapidly during the final project year.

Table 2: PLATOON Website Statistics (M1-M24)

Website Stats	TOTAL (M1-M24)
Visits	12,809
Unique Visitors	8,958
Page Views	46,606
Unique Page Views	31,933
No. published Blog Posts	30
No. published Interviews	12
No. published Press Releases	8 (32 overall translated PRs)

⁷ 8 press releases have been published in total, as per M24.

3.1.2 Press Releases

During the second project year (M13-M24), 6 PLATOON Press Releases have been published on the PLATOON website and actively promoted via PLATOON’s SoMe accounts, as well as distributed via the networks of all Consortium partners and CORDIS. As a result, a total of **8 press releases** were published in the past two years and the KPI defined in the GA was already fulfilled at this point. Further below, two examples are shown to demonstrate the promotion of the press releases.

The third PLATOON Press Release has been published on the project website in M13 and M14 in four (4) different languages of Consortium partners and beyond. **English**⁸, **German**⁹, **Spanish**¹⁰, and **Italian**¹¹.

Figure 1: 3rd PLATOON Press Release on the website

⁸ <https://platoon-project.eu/press-release-the-eu-funded-h2020-project-platoon-is-looking-for-bottom-up-projects-to-help-digitising-the-energy-sector/>

⁹ <https://platoon-project.eu/pressemittteilung-das-von-der-eu-geforderte-h2020-projekt-platoon-sucht-bottom-up-projekte-die-bei-der-digitalisierung-des-energiesektors-helfen-sollen/>

¹⁰ <https://platoon-project.eu/nota-de-prensa-el-proyecto-platoon-financiado-por-la-comision-europea-en-el-programa-h2020-busca-proyectos-para-contribuir-a-digitalizar-el-sector-energetico/>

¹¹ <https://platoon-project.eu/comunicato-stampa-prima-open-call/>

The seventh PLATOON Press Release has been published in M22 and M23 in five (5) different European languages: **English**¹², **German**¹³, **Spanish**¹⁴, **Italian**¹⁵, and **Serbian**¹⁶.

Figure 2: 7th PLATOON Press Release on the website

¹² <https://platoon-project.eu/press-release-2nd-open-call-the-eu-funded-h2020-project-platoon-is-looking-for-bottom-up-projects-to-help-digitising-the-energy-sector/>

¹³ <https://platoon-project.eu/pressemitteilung-zweiter-platoon-open-call-das-von-der-eu-finanzierte-h2020-projekt-platoon-sucht-nach-bottom-up-projekten-die-zur-digitalisierung-des-energiesektors-beitragen/>

¹⁴ <https://platoon-project.eu/nota-de-prensa-2a-open-call-el-proyecto-platoon-financiado-por-la-comision-europea-en-el-programa-h2020-busca-proyectos-para-contribuir-a-digitalizar-el-sector-energetico/>

¹⁵ <https://platoon-project.eu/comunicato-stampa-2-open-call-il-progetto-h2020-platoon-finanziato-dallue-cerca-progetti-per-favorire-la-digitalizzazione-del-settore-energetico/>

¹⁶ <https://platoon-project.eu/saopstenje-drugi-otvoreni-poziv/>

3.2 Social Media

3.2.1 Twitter

Just as during the first project year, the PLATOON TW account¹⁷ has been used to attract the general public that were interested in topics such as energy, sustainability, efficiency, innovation, digitalisation, among others. On top of that, TW has actively been used to attract stakeholders that were directly involved into the energy sector, as well as TW accounts of different DGs of the European Commission. Due to the fact that there was a character restriction for the tweets, the posts on TW were significantly shorter and the language was easier than f.e. on LI.

3.2.1.1 Twitter Statistics January - June 2021 (M13-M18)

Figure 3: PLATOON Twitter Stats December 2020 (M12) - complete version

¹⁷ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU

Table 3: PLATOON Twitter Stats for the first project year 2020 (M1-M12)

Twitter Stats	Total (M1-M12 ¹⁸)
Tweets	360
Impressions	541.5K
Profile Visits	28.96K
Mentions	317
Total Number of Followers	628

Figure 4: PLATOON Twitter Stats January 2021 (M13)

¹⁸ D9.3 has been submitted in M12. Therefore, D9.4 includes the final stats for M12 and the first project year (M1-M12) altogether.

Figure 5: PLATOON Twitter Stats February 2021 (M14)

Figure 6: PLATOON Twitter Stats March 2021 (M15)

Figure 7: PLATOON Twitter Stats April 2021 (M16)

Figure 8: PLATOON Twitter Stats May 2021 (M17)

Figure 9: PLATOON Twitter Stats June 2021 (M18)

Table 4: PLATOON Twitter Stats M13 - M18 (incl. updated stats for M12)

	M12 ¹⁹	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
Tweets	20	24	24	26	12	12	11
Impressions	33.2K	40.6K	39.9K	51.9K	24.8K	21K	19K
Profile Visits	2,526	2,479	3,286	3,520	2,598	1,792	1,881
Mentions	27	46	39	48	27	37	25
New Followers	39	82	73	54	31	29	12

¹⁹ Complete Stats for M12, since D9.3 has been submitted on 11.12.2020.

3.2.1.2 Twitter Statistics July - December 2021 (M19-M24)

Figure 10: PLATOON Twitter Stats July 2021 (M19)

Figure 11: PLATOON Twitter Stats August 2021 (M20)

Figure 12: PLATOON Twitter Stats September 2021 (M21)

Figure 13: PLATOON Twitter Stats October 2021 (M22)

Figure 14: PLATOON Twitter Stats November 2021 (M23)

Table 5: PLATOON Twitter Stats M19 - M24

	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Tweets	11	4	2	19	7	9
Impressions	17.5K	7,313	4,456	9,295	6,468	4,330
Profile Visits	3,959	550	1,073	1,493	2,092	1,951
Mentions	30	17	33	43	13	13
New Followers	25	11	19	8	19	3

Table 6: PLATOON Twitter Stats for the second project year 2021 (M13-M24)

Twitter Stats	Total (M13-M24²⁰)
Tweets	161
Impressions	246.5K
Profile Visits	26.6K
Mentions	371
Total Number of Followers	366

Table 7: PLATOON Twitter Stats for 2020 - 2021 (M1-M24)

Twitter Stats	Total (M1-M24²¹)
Tweets	521
Impressions	788K
Profile Visits	55.56K
Mentions	688
Total Number of Followers	994

²⁰ Status: 13.12.2021. The complete TW stats for M24 will be presented in D9.5.

²¹ Incl. M24 stats as per 13.12.2021. The complete stats for M24 will be presented in D9.5.

3.2.2 LinkedIn

As in the previous year, the PLATOON LI company page has been used to attract businesspersons and experts, esp. from the energy domain. Since the character restriction allowed creating significantly longer posts compared to f.e. tweets, the corresponding LI posts were much more detailed than the posts on TW. In addition, more technical and business-related terms were used for the LI posts.

Below is an overview of the PLATOON LI Stats for the previous year (including the complete data for M12²²).

Table 8: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for the First Project Year 2020 (M1 - M12)

	TOTAL (M1 - M12²³)
Page Views	4,839
Unique Visitors	1,682
Impressions	66K
Unique Impressions	29.76K
Clicks	1,719
Reactions	2,579
Comments	93
Shares	686
Engagement Rate	8.28%
New Followers	1,129

Further below is a detailed presentation of the PLATOON LI stats for the current year (M13-M24).

²² Complete Stats for M12, since D9.3 has been submitted on 11.12.2020.

²³ D9.3 has been submitted in M12. Therefore, D9.4 includes the final stats for M12 and the first project year (M1-M12) altogether.

3.2.2.1 LinkedIn Statistics January - June 2021 (M13 - M18)

Table 9: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats M13 - M18 (incl. updated stats for M12)

	M12 ²⁴	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
VISITORS							
Page Views	242	513	414	349	270	272	235
Unique Visitors	114	196	161	169	106	93	99
UPDATES							
Impressions	6,480	9,717	11,040	11,033	6,422	6,130	6,020
Unique Impressions	3,872	5,502	7,446	7,848	4,468	3,800	2,861
Clicks	81	232	218	197	103	83	136
Reactions	297	332	347	505	297	240	270
Comments	23	17	10	5	0	1	6
Shares	53	90	72	61	49	32	41
Engagement Rate	7.01%	6.91%	5.85%	6.96%	6.99%	5.81%	7.52%
FOLLOWERS							
New Followers	100	126	101	101	53	31	34

²⁴ Complete Stats for M12, since D9.3 has been submitted on 11.12.2020.

3.2.2.2 LinkedIn Statistics July - December 2021 (M19 - M24)

Table 10: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats M19 - M24

	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24 ²⁵
VISITORS						
Page Views	292	118	261	223	174	110
Unique Visitors	140	53	98	115	87	59
UPDATES						
Impressions	6,469	2,215	2,152	6,462	4,692	5,848
Unique Impressions	3,987	1,538	1,114	3,731	2,931	3,222
Clicks	144	60	63	117	109	103
Reactions	253	81	66	307	197	209
Comments	5	1	6	8	3	9
Shares	43	20	15	52	27	12
Engagement Rate	6.88%	7.31%	6.97%	7.49%	7.16%	5.67%
FOLLOWERS						
New Followers	64	19	29	33	32	20

²⁵ Status: 13.12.2021. The complete LI stats for M24 will be presented in D9.5.

Table 11: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for the Second Project Year 2021 (M13 - M24)

	TOTAL (M13 - M24²⁶)
Page Views	3,231
Unique Visitors	1,376
Impressions	73K
Unique Impressions	45.5K
Clicks	1,565
Reactions	5,683
Comments	71
Shares	567
Engagement Rate	6.9%
New Followers	643

Table 12: PLATOON LinkedIn Stats for 2020 - 2021 (M1 - M24)

	TOTAL (M1 - M24²⁷)
Page Views	8,070
Unique Visitors	3,058
Impressions	139K
Unique Impressions	75.2K
Clicks	3,284
Reactions	5,474
Comments	164
Shares	1,253
Engagement Rate	7.59%
New Followers	1,772

²⁶ Status: 13.12.2021. The complete LI stats for M24 will be presented in D9.5.

²⁷ Incl. M24 stats as per 13.12.2021. The complete stats for M24 will be presented in D9.5.

Figure 15: Cumulated Number of PLATOON Followers - LinkedIn & Twitter (M12 – M23)

Figure 16: Cumulated Number of PLATOON Followers - LinkedIn & Twitter (M1 – M23)

3.2.3 YouTube

The ESWC EU Project Networking Session, which has been organized by TIB-KTT in M18 has been actively promoted on the YouTube channel of the PLATOON project. In total, 9 H2020 projects - including PLATOON - had the chance to briefly present their respective projects and to network & connect with the participants afterwards.

Figure 17: The YouTube channel of PLATOON and the uploaded ESWC EU Project Networking Session video

A video campaign presenting the PLATOON partners has been initiated by TIB-KTT and the respective short videos (each of them about 2-3 minutes) will be promoted on PLATOON’s YouTube channel within the third project year (M25-M36).

Figure 18: Michael Fribus presented PLATOON during the ESWC EU Project Networking Session 2021

3.3. Communication and Dissemination Campaigns

The Interviews Campaign, which was prepared during the last project year, has been actively promoted on both the PLATOON LI and TW accounts. In total, **12 interviews** with different members of the PLATOON Consortium were published and promoted on SoMe (see examples in Figure 19 as well as Figure 20 below).

Figure 19: PLATOON Interviews Campaign on LI

Figure 20: PLATOON Interviews Campaign on TW

3.4 Events

3.4.1 Fairs & Online Conferences

During the second year of the H2020 PLATOON project, the Consortium partners took part in several online fairs and conferences as well as physical events. Several different topics in the sphere of the energy sector such as energy efficiency in buildings and the Renovation Wave, innovative technologies in the renewable energy industry, the emerging hydrogen sector in Europe, among others. Furthermore, the PLATOON partners also visited events with a focus on sustainability and ecology, as well as events on the digitalisation of many different tech industries - including the energy sector.

3.4.2 Overview of the PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2021 (M13-M24)

Table 13 presents an overview with all **28 events**²⁸ that the PLATOON partners visited during the second project year (M13-M24).

Table 13: PLATOON Fairs & Online Conferences in 2021 (M13 - M24)

No.	EVENT	DATE	PLACE	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE	PARTICIPATING PLATOON PARTNERS
1.	Kick-Off Event zum Europäischen Klimapakt	20 January	Online	A kick-off session addressing the EU Climate Pact for EU's Citizens, Communes & Organizations.	https://twitter.com/EUinDE/status/1349351969144635392	TIB-KTT
2.	European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) 2021	26 - 27 January	Online	The EDIH GEARING UP conference is a public event organised as the first yearly European Digital Innovation Hubs conference. In coordination with the Luxembourg Ministry of Economy this first year's edition will officially kick-start the European Digital Innovation Hubs initiative all across Europe.	https://event.e-dih.eu/	TIB-KTT
3.	EU Industry Days	23 - 26 February	Online	EU Industry Days is Europe's flagship annual event in industry. It serves as the main platform to discuss	https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/business-and-	TIB-KTT

²⁸ TIB-KTT has visited 21 events during the period M13-M24.

				industrial challenges and co-develop opportunities and policy responses in an inclusive dialogue with a wide range of partners.	industry/eu-industry-days_en	
4.	BRIDGE General Assembly	2 - 4 March	Online	The BRIDGE General Assembly in 2021 presents the latest developments of the initiative. It is the occasion to present the latest activities by the BRIDGE Working Groups and Task Forces during the last period, as well as discover the new BRIDGE projects and hear about the results and lessons learned from completed projects.	https://www.h2020-bridge.eu/2021-bridge-general-assembly-takes-place-on-march-2nd-3rd-and-4th/	TIB-KTT
5.	IoT Tribe Connected Places Accelerator Launch	15 March	Online	An online event by the ecosystem builder IoT Tribe, addressing the transition towards the Net Zero Economy of various European sectors.	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/iot-tribe-connected-places-accelerator-launch-tickets-142252006581?keep_tld=1	TIB-KTT
6.	Climate-neutral and Sustainable Smart Cities - Horizon Europe	16 March	Online	The Climate-neutral and Sustainable Smart Cities D4P Horizon Europe webinar is gathering top experts from the European Commission, industry and academia to present and discuss how energy-efficient technologies, mechanisms, and policies must be put in place at several levels to ensure green digital transformation and the recovery of our society and economy.	https://digital4planet.org/event/digital-for-planet-webinar-climate-neutral-and-sustainable-smart-cities-horizon-europe/	TIB-KTT
7.	2021 IEEE International Forum on Smart Grids for Smart Cities	17 - 23 March	Online	The aim of this online conference was to organise a premier event with keynotes and panel sessions, featuring about 50 notable speakers, each providing a unique international perspective on technology, applications, standards and policy pertaining to Smart Grids as enablers for Smart Cities and other Smart Community solutions.	https://ieeesg4sc.org/	CEPV
8.	WindEurope Sofa	18 March	Online	In this Sofa Talk WindEurope discusses how community	https://windeurope.org/	TIB-KTT

	Talks: Community engagement and its important role in gaining public support for wind farms			engagement affects public support for wind projects. How do wind energy developers involve communities during the planning and construction phases.	about-wind/campaigns/sofa-talks/	
9.	BDVA/DAIRO Activity Group meeting 43	18 March	Online	BDVA/DAIRO organized its Activity Group (AG43) meeting. The meeting brings together the BDVA/DAIRO members and BDV PPP projects as well as other relevant initiatives, focusing particularly on Data Platforms, Data Spaces, Data Governance and Standards and Trustworthiness of Industrial AI.	https://www.bdva.eu/node/1752	ENGIE
10.	The World Energy Leaders Virtual Summit	23 March	Online	The World Energy Leaders Virtual Summit brings a full day of interactive live-streamed panel discussions and workshops to connect, benchmark and learn from the world's most influential minds in the Energy Industry, all online.	https://www.industryiot.com/virtual-summit-form	TIB-KTT
11.	Digitalization of the user-centric Energy System: the use case of electric mobility	31 March	Online	InterConnect will organise a session named "Digitalization of the user-centric Energy System: the use case of electric mobility", on March 31, from 2:30 pm to 5 pm (CET). Different players of this ecosystem will join the session – from a representative from the Portuguese government (under the auspices of the Portuguese presidency of the EU council), European Commission, associations, consumers and representatives from R&D, grid agents, to manufacturers of electric vehicles, among others.	https://interconnectproject.eu/events/digitalization-of-the-user-centric-energy-system-the-use-case-of-electric-mobility/	CEPV
12.	Technology & Business Cooperation Days 2021	12 April - 15 April	Online	Innovation. Inspiration. Interaction. Under the key theme of "Industrial Transformation", exhibitors and industry thought leaders will present their technologies and ideas for the factories, energy systems and supply chains of the future.	https://technology-business-cooperation-days-2021.b2match.io/	TIB-KTT

13.	Berliner Energietage 2021	21 - 23 April 28 - 30 April	Online	The Berliner Energietage is the largest conference event and associated trade fair in Germany in the field of energy system transformation. The participants from all over Germany come from politics, associations, public institutions and industry.	https://www.energietag.de/home.html	TIB-KTT
14.	NGIoT Thematic Workshop: Energy	18 May 2021	Online	This workshop on Energy is part of a thematic workshop series on IoT and Edge computing, organised by the NGIoT and EU-IoT Coordination and Support Actions in collaboration with the European Commission and relevant associations, networks, and projects.	https://www.ngiot.eu/event/ngiot-thematic-workshop-energy/?instance_id=146	ComSensus
15.	Building the Internet of Humans	18 - 19 May 2021	Online	The NGI Forum 2021 is the flagship event of the Next Generation Internet initiative, which brings together some of Europe's top internet innovators who are shaping the Internet of Humans.	https://www.ngi.eu/event/ngi-forum-2021/	TIB-KTT
16.	ESWC EU Project Networking Session 2021	7-10 June 2021	Online	An online live session organized by TIB-KTT. Various H2020 projects met during this conference and presented their respective projects (including PLATOON). This live session offered networking opportunities to the participants.	https://2021.eswc-conferences.org/call-for-networking-session-of-eu-funded-projects/	TIB-KTT
17.	IDSA Summit	22 - 23 June 2021	Online	At the IDSA Summit on June 22 & 23 the IDSA members presented their most convincing success stories. Together with them they have shown the biggest assets and achievements – the rule book, the IDS certification, our open-source strategy, the adoption accelerator – as well as how strongly they are anchored in European and global activities towards data spaces.	https://internationaldata-spaces.org/idsa-summit-2021/	TIB-KTT
18.	ENERGETIKA 2021 (Conference and Exhibition)	22 - 25 June	Zlatibor, Serbia	ENERGETIKA is an annual event of the Serbian Association of Energy Sector Specialists. The event gathers the major stakeholders from Serbia and the Region.	http://savezenergeticara.org/images/pdf/Prvi_poziv_EN2021.pdf	IMP

19.	STARTS in Motion	30 June	Online	This year, a public session was held in the frame of STARTS in MOTION about: "EU funding for art-tech projects - some tips to get closer". Within this session, participants have been provided with tailor-made info on the types of EU funding that match the art-tech projects.	https://www.starts.eu/st-arts-in-motion/	TIB-KTT
20.	CG CIGRE Conference	28 - 30 September	Becici, Montenegro	CG KO CIGRE is a scientific event of the Montenegrin Section of CIGRE that targets the major stakeholders from the energy sector from Montenegro and the Region.	http://cigre.me/en_news.php?id=183	IMP
21.	EU-Russia Exchange on Sustainable Building Policies and Measures - Workshop 2 by BPIE Buildings EU	21 October	Online	The second workshop of the EU-Russia exchange on sustainable building policies and measures facilitates an exchange between stakeholders and practitioners to identify, understand and promote solutions for the renovation of large apartment blocks.	https://www.bpie.eu/event/workshop-scaling-up-the-renovation-of-large-apartment-blocks-technological-and-financing-solutions/	TIB-KTT
22.	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2021	25 - 29 October	Online	The EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW) takes place under the theme: 'Towards 2030: Reshaping the European Energy System'.	http://eusew.eu/	TIB-KTT
23.	DIHNET Project Final EVENT	26 October	Online	After three successful years, DIHNET is arriving at the end of its lifetime as an EU-funded project. DIHNET wants to invite stakeholders to discuss the main project highlights, and to share visions on the future and shape of the EU Digital Innovation Hub ecosystem.	https://dihnet.eu/2021/10/dihnet-final-event-future-and-shape-of-the-eu-dih-ecosystem/	TIB-KTT
24.	Wind Europe Electric City	23 - 25 November	Copenhagen	The main event for wind energy worldwide in 2021, covering both onshore and offshore wind with a special focus on how wind can help electrify heating, transport and industry.		CEPV
25.	European Big Data	29	Online	Organised by the BDVA and the European Commission	https://european-big-	TIB-KTT

	Value Forum 2021	November - 3 December		(DG CNECT), The European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI. EBDVF 2021 theme is “Digital Transformation powered by Data and AI”.	data-value-forum.eu/	
26.	Enlit Europe 2021	30 November - 2 December	Milan	Enlit is a constantly growing, inclusive and end-to-end forum that addresses every aspect of the energy agenda. A community that for 365-days a year collaborates and innovates to solve the most pressing issues in energy.	https://www.enlit-europe.com/live	CEPV
27.	2nd Data Sharing Winter School	7 - 9 December	Online	In 12 sessions, experts present new technologies, scientists will talk about the state of research, and practitioners will show innovative mobility solutions to urban problems, such as the Mobility Data Space, one of Europe’s lighthouse projects.	https://hopin.com/event/s/2nd-data-sharing-winter-school	TIB-KTT
28.	DSBA - Brokering event DEP Data for EU	16 December	Online	The European Commission has launched a number of open calls as part of the Digital Europe Programme (DEP) that are designed to support the building of data spaces in many different sectors. This is an online brokerage event for organisations that can benefit from those open calls under Data for EU work strand under Digital Europe Programme (DEP). The event gives participants the opportunity to discover, connect and engage with other organisations having the same interests.	https://dsba-brokering-data-spaces.b2match.io/	TIB-KTT

3.5 Open Calls (FBA)

The PLATOON project has two open calls (OC). The 1st OC has been successfully finalised with a deadline on March 4, 2021. The 2nd OC launched on October 1, 2021, with a deadline on December 1, 2021. The following subsections will give a brief overview of the dissemination activities that were conducted for the 1st OC and are planned for the 2nd OC.

3.5.1 First Open Call

This OC’s dissemination activities are thoroughly discussed in D7.2, D7.3 as well as D7.5, however, a short overview will be given in this deliverable as well.

For the dissemination of this open call, we primarily utilised FBA/FBC’s networks and worked with TIB in disseminating across PLATOON’s social media channels. FBC also ran a social media campaign to complement the efforts of the PLATOON Consortium. All materials were shared for re-posting by other members of the consortium across their networks, for instance the dissemination through OPEN DEI initiative and its Working Group 3 on Linking Ecosystems by the Basque Energy Cluster was carried out. Furthermore, the PLATOON Consortium also widely disseminated the Open Call through webinars.

Various dissemination activities, e.g. Twitter and LinkedIn posts, promotions on IDSA and on the Sunrise Valley Digital Innovation Hub websites, can be seen on figures below.

Figure 21: Promotion of the 1st PLATOON Open Call on Twitter

Figure 22: Promotion of the 1st PLATOON Open Call on LinkedIn

Figure 23: Promotion of the 3rd PLATOON Press Release re. the 1st PLATOON Open Call on Twitter in various languages

Figure 24: Promotion of the 3rd PLATOON Press Release re. the 1st PLATOON Open Call on LinkedIn in various languages

Figure 25: Promotion of the Q&A Session re. the 1st PLATOON Open Call

Figure 26: Promotion of the 1st PLATOON Open Call updates on 11. & 12. March 2021 on Twitter

PLATOON #DigitalEnergy Project @PLATOON_EU

The 1st #H2020 @PLATOON_EU is closed & we have some exciting updates to share ⚡:

- **267** applications were initiated 📝
- of which **96** applications were submitted 💡
- from **23** different countries 🌍!

More **i** here 🖱️ bit.ly/2OfQZpT #energytransition #innovation

267 applications initiated
96 applications submitted
23 countries
Top 8

Country	Count
Spain	10
Italy	8
Greece	5
France	4
Germany	3
Belgium	2
UK	1
Serbia	1

FundingBox and 9 others

11:37 AM · Mar 12, 2021 · Twitter Web App

View Tweet activity

6 Retweets 13 Likes

PLATOON #DigitalEnergy Project @PLATOON_EU · 6h

Replying to @PLATOON_EU

The top **8** countries sending applications for the @PLATOON_EU #OpenCall were:

- Spain
- Italy
- Greece
- France
- Germany
- Belgium
- UK
- Serbia

More on our project website 🖱️ bit.ly/3I7dZmW
 #innovation #digitalization #AI @Vattel @ids_association @DataEcoEU

🗨️ 5 🍷 6 📤 📄

Figure 27: Promotion of the 1st PLATOON Open Call updates on 11. & 12. March 2021 on LinkedIn

Figure 28: Promotion of the PLATOON Open Call on the IDSA website²⁹

Figure 29: IDSA LI post re. the 1st PLATOON Open Call

²⁹ Cf. <https://internationaldataspaces.org/platoon-launches-the-first-open-call-to-develop-an-open-source-ids-connector/>

Figure 30: IDSA TW post re. the 1st PLATOON Open Call

Figure 31: PLATOON Open Call promo on the Sunrise Valley Digital Innovation Hub website³⁰

³⁰ Cf. <https://sunrisevalleydih.lt/en/kvietimai/4-open-calls-for-digitalization-projects/>

Figure 32: Business Insider promoted Barbara IoT, one of PLATOON's 1st OC Winners

BUSINESS INSIDER Economía Tecnología Estrategia Política Más temas

Barbara IoT, la única firma española que participará en un proyecto financiado con fondos europeos para crear un mercado energético y de datos en la UE

Alberto R. Aguirre 12 jul. 2021 6:30h.

Isidro Nistal, CPO; y David Parón, CEO de Barbara IoT.

- Barbara IoT ha sido una de las seis compañías elegidas (de entre más de 500 en toda Europa) para participar en el consorcio Platoon.
- El proyecto busca probar dos pilotos en 9 meses de un mercado europeo de energía y datos que optimice las redes eléctricas y las hagan más sostenibles.
- La startup española de ciberseguridad en dispositivos conectados garantizará que los datos sobre consumo y electricidad naveguen de forma segura en los grids.

It is worth mentioning that Business Insider promoted PLATOON's 1st Open Call and in particular one of its winners called Barbara IoT on their website³¹ as can be seen above.

3.5.2 Second Open Call

The dissemination activities for the second open call (OC) include the following:

- Preparation stage,
- Launch of the OC,
- Communication activities during the open call to attract applicants,
- Final press release and infographic illustrating the main results of the OC.

The preparation stage involves the development of a communication toolkit that will be sent to the partners, so that they can also promote the open call. The toolkit consists of a press

³¹ <https://www.businessinsider.es/barbara-iot-participara-proyecto-europeo-sistema-electrico-896553>

release, visuals adjusted to social media channels, sample social media posts and a timeline. The OC will be announced on the PLATOON website, with a direct link to the Open Call micro-site with further details about the call, as well as access to the application form.

Once the open call is launched on the 1st of October 2021, several open call announcements will be made (e.g. press releases, FundingBox MoneyBox Newsletter, dissemination through Ambassadors and Supportive Partners).

Throughout the open call, there will be regular social media posts and other types of open call dissemination activities, such as a live Q&A session with potential applicants, info corners in world-class events at EU Level etc. The live Q&A session will include a brief presentation of the project, the open call requirements, and a slot for potential applicants' time, where they can ask questions. The sessions will be recorded for participants to be able to play the web-stream video recording at any time. Online paid ad campaigns will also be used to target specific regions or groups to encourage and secure the number of applications.

Once the open call closes, a press release with an infographic informing the results of the number of applications will be published and sent to media outlets.

Figure 33: Promotion of the 2nd PLATOON Open Call on Twitter

Figure 34: Promotion of the 2nd PLATOON Open Call on LinkedIn

Figure 35: Promotion of the 7th PLATOON Press Release re. the 2nd PLATOON Open Call on Twitter in various languages

Figure 36: Promotion of the 7th PLATOON Press Release re. the 2nd PLATOON Open Call on LinkedIn in various languages

Figure 37: Promotion of the 2nd PLATOON Open Call updates on 6th of December 2021 on Twitter

Figure 38: Promotion of the 2nd PLATOON Open Call updates on 6th of December 2021 on LinkedIn

3.6 Ambassadors (FBA)

Ambassadors are responsible for contributing towards the PLATOON community, the PLATOON website, newsletter and our social media channels, engaging with other members. PLATOON is engaging three Ambassadors to advocate about the project, with a one-year contract commencing from mid-May 2021. This Ambassador programme will enable us to boost the community growth, focusing on a range of consolidated figures in the domain involved in the project to create awareness through their digital channels, as well as in physical events.

The Ambassadors selected for this project are:

1. Nathalie Mitton from **Inria**
2. Jad Nassar from **Yncreá**
3. Thorsten Huelsmann from **International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)**

We will continue working with these ambassadors until mid-May 2022.

Figure 39: PLATOON Website - Ambassadors

3.7 Supportive Partners Programme (FBA)

The Supportive Partners Programme for communities involves entities from across Europe, such as start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem. The Supportive Partners are stakeholders interested in disseminating the project in a win-win cooperation mode. These are identified via community mapping, starting from the PLATOON partners' networks. The list of Supportive Partners is presented in the table below.

Table 14: List of the PLATOON Supportive Partners

No.	Name	Country	Brief Description	Website
1	Big Data Value Association (BDVA)	Belgium	The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with more than 200 members all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations.	https://www.bdva.eu/
2	BerriUp Aceleradora de Startups	Spain	BerriUp Aceleradora de Startups is the first private startup accelerator in the Basque Country. The Donostia-based company, founded in 2015, seeks to support entrepreneurs in launching their projects on the market by accompanying them in the process of validating the business, collaborating with institutional initiatives in the public sector.	https://www.berriup.com/
3	EIT InnoEnergy	Netherlands	EIT InnoEnergy is the leading engine for innovation and entrepreneurship in sustainable energy, across Europe and beyond.	https://www.innoenergy.com/
4	Stara Zagora Regional Economic Development	Bulgaria	The main objective of SZ REDA is to support the development and implementation of mechanisms to manage the process of successful integration into the European community of local and regional authorities and businesses in the region through policy development at a regional and local	https://szeda.eu/en/

	Agency, SZ REDA		level aimed at sustainable development and stimulating economic development.	
5	Tenerrdis Energy Cluster	France	Tenerrdis Energy Cluster supports sustainable economic growth in the new energy technology industries and coordinates a network spanning industry, government, academia, and scientific research to address the challenges of the energy transition.	https://www.tenerrdis.fr/en/
6	Vestbee	Poland	Vestbee is the biggest online matchmaking platform for startups and scaleups in Central & Eastern Europe supported by the global community of VC funds, corporates, business angels and accelerators such as Amazon, HubSpot, InnoEnergy, Engie, Credo Ventures, Next Road Ventures, Tera Ventures, EIT Digital or SABIC.	https://www.vestbee.com/
7	WeSmart	Belgium	WeSmart is a Belgium scale-up founded by specialists with a long experience in the energy and environment sector that has developed a digital platform “as a service” to fully manage energy communities.	http://www.wesmart.com/en
8.	Enagas	Spain	Enagas is a Spanish energy company and European transmission system operator (TSO), which owns and operates the nation’s gas grid. The firm also owns four liquefied natural gas regasification terminals in the country, at Huelva, Barcelona, Cartagena, and Gijon.	https://www.enagas.es/portal/site/enagas
9.	REENGEN	Turkey	REENGEN is a high-tech company established in 2013. Reengen’s Energy IoT Platform is a cloud based PaaS data analytics solution for commercial buildings, industrial facilities and renewable energy plants.	http://www.reengen.com/
10.	International Data Spaces Association	Germany	The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) is a coalition of more than 130 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies self-determine usage rules and realize the full value of their data in secure, trusted, equal partnerships; and we are making that vision a reality. The aim of	https://internationaldataspaces.org/

			<p>IDSA is a global standard for international data spaces (IDS) and interfaces, as well as fostering the related technologies and business models that will drive the data economy of the future across industries.</p>	
11.	Elblox AG	Switzerland	<p>Elblox AG develops and runs digital energy transaction platforms that are used for delivering renewable energy from producers directly to consumers. Elblox AG creates a new customer experience for energy by tracing energy back to its source, visualization of energy flows, monitoring consumption and/or generation, and providing tools to manage cost or invoices in real-time.</p>	https://www.elblox.com/
12.	ASBA Foundation	Armenia	<p>The National Social Housing Association (ASBA) was established in Armenia as a result of Dutch-Armenian Cooperation. Its aims are to develop social housing stock; to become a social entrepreneur by applying sound business principles in developing and managing social housing to achieve their social goals; to attract capital for the social rental stock; to introduce innovative sustainable management of new and existing housing; to manage the social housing stock independently, professionally and cost-efficiently; to make a profit on management and commercial activities related to housing in order to reinvest in social housing development.</p>	http://www.asba.am/
13.	ENLINE Transmission	Portugal	<p>ENLINE Transmission is the brand name of GML’s technology and software solutions. ENLINE provides an innovative Digital Twin sensor-less technology with advanced analytic and diagnostic algorithms to exploit the untapped potential of your transmission assets.</p>	https://www.enline-transmission.com/
14.	SPRI Group	Spain / Basque Country	<p>SPRI Group works with companies to facilitate access to digitalisation, cybersecurity and helps to set up companies. SPRI helps to look at the best way of expanding one’s business in other countries or to look for physical spaces, pavilions, or offices where customers can set up their companies. SPRI has resources to face any challenge and a global vision that helps to lead the way.</p>	https://www.spri.eus/en/

15.	Inwebit	Poland	Inwebit is a technology partner in digital transformation. Started as a custom software development company Inwebit evolved to business-oriented, aware of the specifics of the industry, product development experts with a broad spectrum of competencies to solve the right problem with the right solution. Inwebit has its own, highly innovative R&D lab, with very talented and experienced engineers, which gave Inwebit the opportunity to not only develop a software part of one's product but to build a product as a whole, with all the electronics and all the integrations that customers need.	https://inwebit.pl/pl/start
16.	Revolve Media	Belgium	REVOLVE MEDIA is dedicated to communicating about water, energy, ecosystems, mobility, and the circular economy. We provide communication support to EU-funded projects and work closely with strategic partners to advance their sustainability projects.	https://revolve.media/
17.	TechnologyCatalogue.com	Netherlands	Discover and deploy technological innovations to accelerate energy transition. That's the objective of TechnologyCatalogue.com. With over 700 technologies and 70,000 unique users of the platform, TechnologyCatalogue.com supports the energy transition by providing a platform that bridges the gap between technology suppliers, end-users and experts, and facilitates technological innovations towards a more sustainable energy sector.	https://www.technologycatalogue.com/
18.	Enermaps	Switzerland	EnerMaps Open Data Management Tool aims to improve data management and accessibility in the field of energy research for the renewable energy industry. EnerMaps' tool accelerates and facilitates the energy transition offering a qualitative and user-friendly digital platform to energy professionals.	https://enermaps.eu/

Figure 40: PLATOON Website - Supportive Partners (Part 1)

PLATOON organises a Supportive Partners Programme to build online communities. This programme targets entities from across Europe, such as start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem.

The Supportive Partners are stakeholders interested in signing a Letter of Engagement to disseminate the project in a win-win cooperation mode.

Below, there is a list presenting our PLATOON Supportive Partners:

Logo	Name	Brief Description
	BDVA	The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organization with more than 200 members all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations. BDVA is the private counterpart to the EU Commission to implement the Big Data Value PPP program. BDVA and the Big Data Value PPP pursue a common shared vision of positioning Europe as the world leader in the creation of Big Data Value. The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and societal benefit, and, achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence.
	BerrUp	BerrUp Acceleratori de Startups is the first private startup accelerator in the Basque Country. The Donostia-based company, founded in 2015, seeks to support entrepreneurs in launching their projects on the market by accompanying them in the process of validating the business, collaborating with institutional initiatives in the public sector.
	EIT InnoEnergy	EIT InnoEnergy is the leading engine for innovation and entrepreneurship in sustainable energy, across Europe and beyond. EIT InnoEnergy has invested in and provided added value services to some 200 sustainable energy-related innovators, of those 20+ are across the hydrogen value chain, and some 40+ in renewable generation, a key component to green hydrogen. Following the mandate of the EU Commission, EIT InnoEnergy is leading the industrial stream of the European Battery Alliance since 2017, a European Commission initiative to build a strong and competitive European battery industry; and with this (OHAC) initiative aims at replicating that success in the green hydrogen revolution.

Figure 41: PLATOON Website - Supportive Partners (Part 2)

Partner Logo	Partner Name	Description
	SZ REDA	Stara Zagora Regional Economic Development Agency, SZ REDA, was established in 1999 as a non-profit organization for the public benefit. The main objective of SZ REDA is to support the development and implementation of mechanisms to manage the process of successful integration into the European community of local and regional authorities and businesses in the region through policies development at a regional and local level aimed at sustainable development and stimulate economic development. For its 25-years history SZ REDA has successfully implemented over 70 projects in various programs and established as a reliable international partner.
	Tenerdu	Tenerdu's Energy Cluster supports sustainable economic growth in the new energy technology industries and coordinates a network spanning industry, government, academia, and scientific research to address the challenges of the energy transition.
	Vestbee	Vestbee is the biggest online matchmaking platform for startups and scaleups in Central & Eastern Europe supported by the global community of VC funds, corporates, business angels and accelerators such as Amazon, HubSpot, InnoEnergy, Engie, Credo Ventures, Next Road Ventures, Tara Ventures, BIT Digital or SABIC. Being the regional pioneer in online startup events, Vestbee hosts CEE Startup & Scaleup Challenges, the biggest 100% ONLINE competitions in Central & Eastern Europe. Vestbee also provides tools for startups to manage fundraising in one place, and for investors, corporates and accelerators to manage deal flow, applications, innovation programs and thanks to Startup Virtual Showroom, online matchmaking.
	WeSmart	WeSmart is a Belgium scale-up founded by specialists with a long experience in the energy and environment sector that has developed a digital platform "as a service" to fully manage energy communities. WeSmart brings together human intelligence, collective participation and technologies to reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions. Also, WeSmart is participating in the energy revolution by providing solutions for energy communities.
	Enagas	Enagas is a Spanish energy company and European transmission system operator (TSO), which owns and operates the nation's gas grid. The firm also owns four liquefied natural gas regasification terminals in the country, at Huelva, Barcelona, Cartagena, and Gijón.
	REEDVDN	REEDVDN is a high-tech company established in 2013. Reengen's Energy IoT Platform is a cloud-based PaaS data analytics solution for commercial buildings, industrial facilities and renewable energy plants. Already collecting data from thousands of buildings in 3 different countries, the data science-centric IoT Platform employs machine learning algorithms and big data analytics in order to provide energy saving, operational efficiency, energy procurement optimization and predictive maintenance for its customers.
	International Data Spaces Association	The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) is a coalition of more than 100 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies self-determine usage rules and realize the full value of their data in secure, trusted, equal partnerships, and we are making that vision a reality. The aim of IDSA is a global standard for international data spaces (IDS) and interfaces, as well as fostering the related technologies and business models that will drive the data economy of the future across industries.

Figure 42: PLATOON Website - Supportive Partners (Part 3)

PLATOON		Home	About PLATOON	Case Study	News & Events	Partners	Risks	Network	Ethics & Security	Contact
	Elblox	Elblox AC develops and deploys energy transaction platforms that are user-friendly, delivering renewable energy from producers directly to consumers. Elblox AC creates a new customer experience for energy by trading energy, hedging resources, visualization of energy flows, monitoring consumption and/or generation, and providing tools to manage solar or wind in real time. The main aim of Elblox AC is to cover energy transaction cost through smart trading and automation. In order to achieve these benefits Elblox AC utilizes smart grid technology.								
	AUSA Foundation	National Trade Housing Association (AUSA) is established in America as a result of United American Cooperation. Its aim is to develop and foster housing industry to become a social entrepreneur by applying sound business principles in developing and managing public housing to achieve their social goals, to attract capital for the social investment to introduce innovative sustainable management of new and existing housing, to manage the social housing assets independently, professionally and cost-efficiently to make workforce management and commercial activities viable in housing in order to revival in social housing development.								
	ENLINE Technology a DNL company	ENL is a company specialized in software development for Power Systems, bringing Power Engineering, Data Science, Artificial Intelligence and IoT to the Power Grid industry. ENL solutions make Power Grids Smarter, Safer, Reliable, Flexible and Greener. The applications and services are smart and profoundly changing the way power grid assets are operated and maintained, increasing security, reducing operation downtime and adding value. ENLINE is the only and largest ENL technology and software solutions. ENLINE provides an innovative Digital Twin power grid technology with advanced analytics and diagnostic algorithms to exploit the untapped potential of your transmission assets.								
	SPRI	SPRI works with companies facilitate access to digitalization, cybersecurity and help to set up companies. SPRI helps to look at the best use of existing assets/business in other countries or to look for strategic assets, locations, or offices where customers can be reached optimally. SPRI has resources to help in meetings and a global view of markets to reach the top.								
	INWOBIT	INWOBIT is a technology partner in digital transformation. INWOBIT is a custom software development company, model oriented to business oriented, aware of the specifics of the industry, product development experts with a broad spectrum of competencies to solve the right problem with the right solution. INWOBIT focuses on highly innovative R&D, with very talented and experienced engineers, which gives INWOBIT the opportunity to recruit, develop a software team of your product but also to act as a whole with all the elements of all the integrative that customer need.								
	REVOLVE MEDIA	REVOLVE MEDIA is a developer communicating about clean energy, ecosystems, mobility and the power economy. We provide communication support to EU funded projects and work closely with strategic partners to advance their sustainability projects. REVOLVE Group includes regional offices and national representation to enhance strategic communication and create content solutions for sustainability projects.								
	Technology Care	Discover and share technological innovations to accelerate energy transition. That's the objective of TechnologyCare.com . With over 100 technologies and 70000 unique users of the platform, TechnologyCare.com supports the energy transition by providing a performance programme for between technology suppliers and users and users, and facilitates technological innovations towards a more sustainable energy sector.								
	EUSA	EUSA (Clean Data Management) has aims to improve data management and accessibility in the field of energy, research for the renewable energy industry. EUSA has tool, website and facilitates the energy transition offering visualization and user-friendly digital platform to energy professionals. The project is based on the facilitation of people (non-renewable data like Energy, Economic, Interconnectivity and Resilience). EUSA project coordinates, enhances the existing energy development and innovation ecosystem, research and to develop an interface between researchers and energy professionals.								

3.8 Mentoring Committee (FBA)

The Mentoring Committee is composed of Technical Mentors, who provide technical mentoring to the Bottom-up Projects. Each project is assigned a dedicated Technical Mentor with whom the project members collaborate throughout the support programme. The performance of each project is evaluated by the Mentoring Committee after each milestone. The evaluation criteria are the following:

- Deliverables' quality.
- Technical performance indicators.
- Deadline Compliance.

Each criterion is scored from 0 to 10, and the threshold is 7 points.

Figure 43: Members of the PLATOON Mentoring Committee

The Mentoring Committee's evaluate the performance of Bottom-up Projects at the Review Milestones after each Technology Transfer stage. The evaluation criteria are the quality of the deliverables, the technology performance indicators as well as the time compliance.

Meet our PLATOON Mentors

Name	Photo	About the Member
Isabella Jank		<p>Dr. Isabella Jank is a Senior Researcher at the Faculty of Informatics, University of Belgiate, Serbia and Associate Professor at the Singuile International University.</p> <p>As a technical engineer, she has been involved in many information systems projects for clients in Serbia and the region. Since 2017, she has participated in many national and international research projects including projects funded by the European Commission. In the last three years, she has acted as a Coordinator of the H2020 project LAMBDA: Learning, Adapting, Multiscale Data Analytics and INHERIT: Capacity building in Smart and Resilient HRSDI management. Currently she serves as an expert evaluation and reviewer of EC Framework Programme Projects and H2020 projects, as a member of Scientific Committees of International Conferences and also reviewer of respective international journals in the domain of Smart City Technologies, Knowledge Management, Business Analytics, Expert Systems, Software Engineering and Innovation.</p> <p>In PLATOON she is a Leader of Pilot 2a (Electrical Balancing and Prediction) Horizontal Team and a Member of the PV Forecasting Technical Team.</p>
Patrick Maurer		<p>Patrick Maurer is a Civil Environmental Engineer with a Master's Degree in environmental engineering and a PhD in Urban Planning Techniques (Université de Savoie).</p> <p>Moreover, he is an expert in urban planning, energy, building, renewable energy, Near Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB), smart economy, impact assessment and risk analysis, evaluation techniques, information technology (such as GIS, BIM, or BIM), hydrology and electrical engineering (with health and safety).</p> <p>Patrick Maurer is also an independent Expert Evaluator and Monitor for the EC (in particular the H2020 programme) and for other institutions. Additionally, he is a lecturer for master's degree courses in Environmental engineering for sustainable development and coordination of the PhD-BIM (Bachelor's) (Savoie). Since 2021, Patrick Maurer is engaged in R&D projects as an expert in project manager (ICT, energy efficiency, NZEB, RES plants but also civil infrastructures) and in international evaluation projects (ERC).</p> <p>Since 2020, he focuses on RES technologies and H2020's urban model, providing both R&D and environmental experiences. Recently he founded a start-up company oriented to the BIM Design of Energy Efficient Buildings with a strong focus on innovation.</p>
Jose Maria Garcia Ramirez		<p>Jose Maria Garcia Ramirez is currently an IT Project Manager for Innovation and Development of Business Digital Transformation, IT and Big Data. In the last 3 years, he has worked on European innovation projects within the H2020, ECSEL and Interim programmes. His areas of expertise are the development of digital platforms and systems, integration of Energy, Transport, Smart Cities and Health.</p> <p>Jose Maria has growing experience in IoT (CPG, Big Data, M2M), IT architectures (SOA, cloud and Aggregating), integration of systems (semantic, quality and services (ITL, Cost and ISO 2002 certifications), the definition of broader standardisation & control of IT transformation strategies.</p>

3.9 Industrial Dissemination (CEPV)

According to the PLATOON Dissemination and Communication Strategy defined in the deliverable D9.1, the industrial dissemination activities in the scope of Task 9.3 are specifically addressed to the following target segments of the energy value chains:

- Developers and/or owners of energy assets
- O&M service providers
- Wind turbine Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs, Tier 1)
- Equipment and components manufacturers (Tier 2 and 3)
- ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) companies
- Research and development centers - testing facilities

In order to reach relevant companies from these target segments, PLATOON partners have kept on carrying out a number of dissemination activities during the second project year (2021), which are reported in the following subsections.

The industrial dissemination and communication activities planned in 2021 have still been impacted by the COVID-19 measures, in particular those events involving physical attendance and large gatherings, such as exhibitions and conferences. Nevertheless, a great effort has been made in the second half of the year to pave the way back to normal and some face-to-face events have been successfully held.

3.9.1 Participation in relevant exhibitions, events and conferences of the energy sector

Again, exhibitions, conferences and large face-to-face events in general have suffered the greatest impact from the COVID-19 measures in 2021, especially during the first half of the year, in which most of these events had to be held fully online.

Participation in IEEE International Forum on Smart Grids for Smart Cities (17-23 March 2021)

CEPV team participated on behalf of PLATOON in this event³², organized by RWTH Aachen, with a virtual booth at the Virtual Exhibition Hall for H2020 Projects. During the 4-day exhibition, requests from the audience at the virtual booth were addressed and project dissemination material was displayed.

In addition to PLATOON, other H2020 projects in the framework of OPEN DEI initiative participated at the event, such as COORDINET, INTERCONNECT, INTERRFACE, ONENET and PLATONE.

³² <https://ieeesg4sc.org/>

Figure 44: PLATOON Virtual Booth at IEEE SG4SC event

Participation in ENERGETIKA 2021 (Belgrade, 6-8 October 2021)

Figure 45: PLATOON presented at ENERGETIKA 2021, Serbia

Figure 46: Networking with stakeholders from SEE at (TRINITY booth, ENERGETIKA 2021, Serbia)

Participation in Wind Europe Electric City (Copenhagen, 23-25 November 2021)

WindEurope Electric City 2021³³ (the 2021 Wind Europe conference and exhibition) took place on 23 - 25 November in Copenhagen. This has been the main event for wind energy worldwide in 2021, covering both onshore and offshore wind with a special focus on how wind can help electrify heating, transport and industry.

In the framework of PLATOON Industrial Dissemination activities, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) booked a **stand in the Innovation Park**³⁴, a pavilion specifically designed to promote research and findings of EU projects. A project poster, a video on a Digital Twin of a Wind Turbine Power Train made by Tecnalia and other dissemination materials were displayed at the booth. The CEPV team was in charge of the booth during the whole exhibition with support from Tecnalia and VUB.

Figure 47: PLATOON Booth at the Innovation Park (Wind Europe Electric City 2021)

³³ <https://windeurope.org/ElectricCity2021/>

³⁴ <https://windeurope.org/ElectricCity2021/exhibition/innovation-park/#eu-project>

In addition to the stand, PLATOON was allocated a speaking slot on Nov 23rd. A presentation on **“Data Analytics Toolbox and Hybrid Digital Twin for Wind Turbines”**, focused on the PLATOON Wind pilot and specifically, on the Digital Twin part was jointly produced by Tecnia and VUB. Participating speakers were Ainhoa Pujana (Tecnia) and Jan Helsen (VUB).

Figure 48: PLATOON Speaking slot at the Innovation Park (Wind Europe Electric City 2021)

Participation in ENLIT (Milan, 30 November-2 December 2021)

Enlit Europe 2021³⁵ - the new unifying brand for European Utility Week & POWERGEN Europe – was held on **Nov 30 – Dec 2 in Milan**. This is the main European event focused on the energy transition from source to generation and from grid to consumer.

In the framework of PLATOON Industrial Dissemination activities, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) booked a **stand for PLATOON in the European Projects Zone**³⁶ (stand: 12.EU11), a pavilion aimed to disseminate research and findings of EU projects. A project poster, brochures, a video on a Digital Twin of a Wind Turbine Power Train made by Tecnia and other dissemination materials were displayed at the booth. The CEPV team oversaw the booth during the whole event with support from Tecnia and ENGIE, answering questions and explaining the project details to the visitors.

Figure 49: PLATOON Booth at the European Projects Zone (ENLIT Europe 2021)

³⁵ <https://www.enlit-europe.com/live>

³⁶ <https://www.enlit-europe.com/learn/eu-projects-zone>

PLATOON was also disseminated at the **Basque Country Pavilion**, coordinated by CEPV and focused on the Basque Smart Grids value chain, involving companies and entities such as Tecnalia, PLATOON Technical Coordinator. A PLATOON poster was displayed at one of the walls and brochure printouts were delivered to interested visitors.

Figure 50: PLATOON dissemination at the Basque Country Pavilion (ENLIT Europe 2021)

Dissemination on the project progress and outcomes was also made through presentations in several sessions and panels held along the 3-day event, such as follows:

- Hub session on **“Energy Data Spaces”**, on Nov 30th co-organized by OPEN DEI and the European Commission. PLATOON speaker was José Ignacio Hormaeche, Industrial Dissemination Lead (*further details provided in chapter 3.9.3*).
- BRIDGE session on **“Interoperability and data exchange to support digitalisation”**, on Dec 1st at the EU Projects Zone (Hall 12). PLATOON speaker was Philippe Calvez, Project Coordinator.

At the BRIDGE session, a booklet with full details about the projects connected to the BRIDGE initiative was delivered to the audience, including also a description of PLATOON.

Last but not least, the 2nd Open Call was disseminated at the PLATOON booth by CEPV team during its last day before the submission deadline (Dec. 1st).

Figure 51: Panellists at BRIDGE session on Dec 1st (ENLIT Europe 2021)

14:00 - 16:00

Interoperability and data exchange to support digitalisation

EU Projects Zone

Chairperson

- Olivier Genest, Chair Data Management Working Group - DG ENER

Speakers

- Mark van Stiphout, Deputy Head of Unit - Research Innovation Competitiveness and Digitalisation - DG Energy - European Commission
- Maher Chebbo, WG4 Co-chair - ETIP SNET
- Esteban Pastor, Representative - ETRA and IANOS Projects
- Conor Murphy, Representative - GridVis Project
- Chloé Fournely, Researcher - XFLEX
- Ferdinando Bosco, Technical Responsible - Platone Project
- George Boultadakis, Representative - INTERRFACE
- Philippe Calvez, Coordinator - PLATOON Project
- Fenareli Lampathaki, Technical Manager - SYNERGY Project
- Alberto Dognini, Representative - OPEN DEI Project
- Ganesh Sauba, Representative - PHOENIX Project
- Mónica Aragón Peñalba, Coordinator - BD4OPEM Project
- Susete Albuquerque, Representative - EUniversal Project

Figure 52: PLATOON presentation at the BRIDGE session on “Interoperability and data exchange to support digitalisation” (ENLIT Europe 2021)

Figure 53: BRIDGE initiative booklet, including PLATOON details (ENLIT Europe 2021)

The participation at the ENLIT event was disseminated through CEPV channels and social networks.

Figure 54: Dissemination of PLATOON activities at ENLIT in social media

3.9.2 Periodic contacts and launch of collaboration initiatives with selected entities and stakeholders

Collaboration and involvement of PLATOON in OPEN DEI³⁷ initiative has continued during 2021, aiming to facilitate interaction, mutual knowledge and exchange of best practices and results between a number of projects specifically focused on providing added value to energy stakeholders through efficient data handling, processing and analysis.

CEPV has continued co-chairing the WG3 on Linking Ecosystems in close cooperation with OPEN DEI management team and with support from the H2020 projects involved, looking to facilitate knowledge sharing, exploit dissemination and promote joint activities to make an efficient use of their allocated resources.

Follow-up meetings of WG3 have been organized and held in Jan 15th, Mar 12th, Apr 23rd, May 28th, Jun 23rd, Sep 9th and Oct 20th, chaired by CEPV and OPEN DEI teams, with participation from the projects involved in the WG and representatives from the European Commission (DG CONNECT).

The most relevant topics discussed in 2021 meetings have been the following:

³⁷ <http://www.opendei.eu/about/#about>

- Projects and pilots presentations (knowledge exchange)
- Information on the Open Calls for cascade funding by participating projects (call details and lessons learnt)
 - PLATOON 1st and 2nd Open calls have been disseminated by CEPV team at the WG3 meetings and related material has been shared with the WG members:
 - Press release delivery for publication on the OPEN DEI website.
 - Ad-hoc presentations with details on the calls.
- Organization of joint dissemination events:
 - “Data sharing and governance for Energy applications” Conference in Bilbao on Sept 23rd, 2021 (*further details provided in chapter 3.9.3*).
 - Workshop on “Energy Data Spaces” at Enlit Conference & Exhibition in Milan on Nov 30th, 2021 (*further details provided in chapter 3.9.3*).

3.9.3 Organisation of workshops and conferences, targeted to industrial European audiences

As a result of the meetings held in the framework of the OPEN DEI WG3, two joint dissemination events have been organized and held in 2021.

PLATOON-OPEN DEI Conference on Data sharing and governance for Energy applications (Bilbao, September 23rd, 2021)

In the framework of the industrial dissemination activities for PLATOON project, the Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) coordinated with the support of ENGIE, TECNALIA and the European OPEN DEI initiative a conference focused on “Data sharing and governance for Energy applications” The event was held on 23rd of September in Bilbao (Basque Country, Spain) and brought together 73 attendees and featured an outstanding panel of technical and institutional speakers.

At the beginning, the event was scheduled for February 2021 but due to covid 2019 constraints and limitations, it was decided to postpone it to September, giving the opportunity to regain some physical proximity and to pave the way back to normal. However, online access was also provided for those participants who were not able to travel yet.

The conference was structured into three sessions:

- Opening session: with representatives from the Basque Government and the European Commission, who set the context for the event.
- Technical sessions: with keynote speakers who provided valuable insights on the technological challenges for energy data sharing and the ongoing initiatives to make it possible.
- Projects and pilots in energy data sharing: with representatives from the H2020 projects involved in OPEN DEI Energy domain, who presented their activity and discussed the needs and challenges that they are facing in order to create a common ground for data sharing in the energy sector.

The full conference agenda is shown here below.

Figure 55: Agenda of the “Conference on Data Sharing and Governance for Energy Applications” event

Conference on Data sharing and governance for Energy applications

Date: 29th September 2021
Venue: Palacio Euskalduna, Bilbao, room 5H TERRAZA <https://www.euzkadi.eus/inter/NewsZut/>

AGENDA

9:00-9:30	CONFERENCE OPENING
9:00-9:15	Institutional opening Cristina Oyón, Director of Technology, Innovation and Sustainability at Grupo SPRI - Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment of the Basque Government
9:15-9:30	Introduction and context for the Conference Mark van Stiphout, Deputy Head of Unit DG ENER/BS Rolf Riemenschneider, Head of Sector IoT, DG CONNECT/E4 European Commission
9:30-13:30 DATA SHARING CHALLENGES	
9:30-10:00	Keynote speech: technological challenges in data sharing for energy applications Erik Maqueda, TECNALIA, PLATOON Technical Coordinator
10:00-10:20	Open DEI Position Paper "Design Principles for Data Spaces" Silvia Castellví, Senior Consultant, IDSA
10:20-10:40	BDVA – Energy Task Force Ana García, Secretary General, BDVA
10:40-11:00	Smart networks in the energy transition Professor Antonello Monti, Institute Director, RWTH Aachen University Valentina Janev, Ph.D. Senior Scientific Associate, Institute Mihajlo Pupin
11:00-11:30 Coffee Break	
11:30-13:30 DATA SPACE INITIATIVES	
11:30-12:00	International Data Space: standard for Data governance Thorsten Huelsmann, CFO, IDSA
12:00-13:00	GAIA-X – Energy Data Space: general presentation and overview of the activities in the Energy Node in the French and German hubs Philippe Calvez, ENGIE
13:00-13:30	Q&A session

13:30-14:30	Networking lunch
14:30-17:00 PROJECTS AND PILOTS IN ENERGY DATA SHARING	
14:30-16:00	"Pitch" presentations of projects that participate in the OPEN DEI Energy domain Working Groups and others invited PLATOON - Philippe Calvez (ENGIE) BD4NRG - Massimo Bertoncini (ENGINEERING) BD4OPEM - Arturo Medela (ATOS) COORDINET - Carlos Medina (TECNALIA) INTERCONNECT - Fabio A. Coelho (INESC TEC) INTERFACE - Nikolaos Bildis (EURODDYN) PLATONE - Antonello Monti (RWTH AACHEN UNIV) SYNERGY - Fenareli Lampathaki (Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions) DAEKIN - Eugenio Perea (TECNALIA)
16:00-16:45	Roundtable: Will the running projects solve the technology gap and the data sharing/access gaps in the energy sector? How will the proposed pilots manage the data governance issues? What is the role of Regional initiatives in boosting and implementing data sharing through the energy value chains? Representatives of the projects, chaired by José Ignacio Hormaeche, General Director of the Basque Energy Cluster and PLATOON Industrial Dissemination Lead
16:45-17:00	Wrap-up: main conclusions and next steps Philippe Calvez, ENGIE, PLATOON Project Coordinator
17:00	End of Conference. Networking

PLATOON and OPEN DEI projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 872592 and No 857065 respectively

Conference Opening

The opening session, led by José Ignacio Hormaeche -Managing Director of the Basque Energy Cluster- was chaired by Cristina Oyón -Director of Technology, Innovation and Sustainability at SPRI-, who was accompanied by Mark van Stiphout -Deputy Unit Director at DG ENERGY- and Rolf Riemenschneider -Director of the IoT Sector at DG CONNECT- representing the European Commission. All of them highlighted the commitment of their respective institutions to digitalisation in the value chains of the energy sector as a catalyst for the energy transition through specific initiatives such as the Basque Digital Innovation Hub (BDIH) in the case of the Basque Government and the Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan (DoEAP) and the Common European Energy Data Space, in the case of the European Commission.

Figure 56: José Ignacio Hormaeche (CEPV), Cristina Oyón (SPRI) and Begoña Molinete (ACE) opening the event

Figure 57: Mark van Stiphout -Deputy Unit Director at DG ENERGY (European Commission)

Figure 58: Rolf Riemenschneider -Director of the IoT Sector at DG CONNECT (European Commission)

Technical sessions

The opening session was followed by two technical panels focusing on the technological challenges in the field of data sharing and the initiatives that are driving it forward at an international level.

Data sharing challenges

Erik Maqueda, Data Analytics expert at TecNALIA and Technical Coordinator of the PLATOON project, identified the technological challenges around Data Spaces as a solution to the existing barriers to digitisation in the energy sector; Silvia Castellví (IDSA) presented the guidelines for the design principles of Data Spaces, agreed within the framework of the OPEN DEI initiative; Prof. Antonello Monti (University of Aachen) and PhD. Valentina Janev (Institute Mihajlo Pupin) respectively discussed the role of smart grids in the energy transition and the activities carried out in this field in Serbia.

Figure 59: Erik Maqueda (TECNALIA), PLATOON Technical Coordinator

Figure 60: Silvia Castellví, Senior Consultant (IDSA)

Figure 61: Professor Antonello Monti (RWTH Aachen University)

Figure 62: Valentina Janev, Ph.D. (Institute Mihajlo Pupin)

Data space initiatives

Regarding the initiatives underway to promote data sharing, their current status and progress in their activity were presented by Ana García on behalf of BDVA (Big Data Value Association), Thorsten Huelsmann on behalf of IDSA (International Data Spaces Association) and Philippe Calvez (ENGIE, Coordinator of the PLATOON project), on behalf of GAIA-X. As a common element in their speech, it is worth highlighting the interest and willingness to collaborate between all the initiatives to move towards a harmonised governance for Data Spaces.

Figure 63: Ana García (BDVA)

Figure 64: Philippe Calvez (ENGIE) and Thorsten Huelsmann (IDSA)

Projects and pilots in energy data sharing

The programme was completed with a pitch session involving eight H2020 projects involved in the OPEN DEI initiative and specifically in the energy domain, with the aim of identifying synergies and opportunities to develop a common knowledge base for data sharing in the coming years. Representatives from PLATOON, BD4NRG, BD4OPEM, COORDINET, INTERCONNECT, INTERFACE, PLATONE and SYNERGY presented their objectives, the technological developments they are working on to respond to the needs of data sharing in the different cases of application in the energy sector and the demonstration pilots planned to validate these developments. They were joined by the Elkartek DAEKIN project, as a regional Basque initiative in the field of data sharing.

Technical visits

As a complement to the conference, a technical visit was organised the day before (Sep 22nd) to the facilities of TECNALIA and the Hubgrade of GIROA VEOLIA - both PLATOON partners - where the participants were able to learn first-hand about the capabilities and activity carried out by both entities.

Figure 65: Technical visits

The conference was disseminated on CEPV website (<http://www.clusterenergia.com/international/cluster-energia-organiza-conferencia-internacional-data-sharing-and-governance-for-energy-applications-en-su-estrategia-impulso-a-dig-3>) and social networks (https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/).

Figure 66: PLATOON-OPEN DEI conference dissemination on CEPV website

23 Sep 2021 The Basque Energy Cluster organises the international conference 'Data sharing and governance for Energy applications' as part of its strategy to promote the digitisation of the energy sector's value chains

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The event, held on 23 September at the Palacio Euskalduna (Bilbao) with the possibility of telematic participation, brought together 73 attendees and featured an outstanding panel of technical and institutional speakers.

The conference 'Data sharing and governance for Energy applications' is part of the dissemination activities for the business segment that the Basque Energy Cluster Association (ACE) coordinates within the H2020 PLATOON project, and was organised with the support of ENGIE, TECNALIA and the European OPEN DEI Initiative.

The opening session, led by José Ignacio Hormaeche - Managing Director of the Basque Energy Cluster - was chaired by Cristina Oyón, Director of Technology, Innovation and Sustainability at SPRI, who was accompanied by Mark van Stiphout, Deputy Unit Director at DG ENERGY and Rolf Riemenschneider, Director of the IoT Sector at DG CONNECT, representing the European Commission. All of them highlighted the commitment of their respective institutions to digitalisation in the value chains of the energy sector as a catalyst for the energy transition through specific initiatives such as the Basque Digital Innovation Hub (BDIH) in the case of the Basque Government and the Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan (DoEAP) and the Common European Energy Data Space, in the case of the European Commission.

Figure 67: PLATOON-OPEN DEI conference dissemination on CEPV social networks

Hub session on “Energy Data Spaces” at Enlit Conference & Exhibition (Milan, November 30th, 2021)

The session was organised in the framework of the OPEN DEI Working Group 3 (WG3) on Linking Ecosystems, with support from Svetoslav Mihaylov, Policy Officer at DG Connect (European Commission). The agenda and the contributions from the different projects and speakers were discussed and aligned through several WG3 meetings along the year.

Table 15: Hub session on “Energy Data Spaces” at Enlit Conference & Exhibition - Agenda

Programme Data Hub DAY 1 (30 November 2021)	
“The “European Strategy for Data”, launched by the European Commission, aims at creating a single market for data to be shared and exchanged across sectors efficiently and securely, having as centerpiece the concept of data spaces. In this session the focus is placed on the energy domain, analyzing the cutting-edge solutions for data management and the architectures for data exchange deployed in the ongoing European initiatives.”	
SESSION: Energy Data Spaces	
Chairperson: Svetoslav Mihaylov	
14.00-14.05	Introduction to OpenDEI

14.05-14.15	10mns introduction on the session logic and speakers by the chairperson
14.15-14.45	Topic title: OpenDEI Data Governance on Data Spaces <i>Speaker: IDSA, Thorsten Hülsmann</i>
14.45-15.05	Topic title: Data Management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BRIDGE work on Data Exchange Architecture • Interoperability • Link to standardisation <i>Speaker: BRIDGE, Olivier Genest</i>
15.05-15:15	Afternoon Coffee Break
15.15-15.30	Topic title: On the Importance of Data Sharing in the Field of Renewable Energies <i>Speaker: PLATOON, José I. Hormaeche</i>
15:30-15:45	Topic title: Semantic Interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • InterConnect's Semantic Interoperability Layer <i>Speaker: InterConnect, David Emanuel Rua</i>
15.45-16.00	Topic title: IEGSA Platform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperable data exchange among TSOs, DSOs and Prosumers <i>Speaker: INTERRFACE, George Boultradakis</i>
16.00-16.15	Topic title: The Potentials of Big Data for Energy: SYNERGY Project <i>Speaker: SYNERGY, Ugo Stecchi</i>
Panel	
16.15-17:00	Panel Discussion: Energy Data Spaces Moderator: Golboo Pourabdollahian (OpenDEI)

PLATOON representative was José Ignacio Hormaeche, Industrial Dissemination Lead, who gave some insights on the importance of data sharing in the field of renewable energies, highlighting the main challenges ahead and how the developments carried out in PLATOON can contribute to overcome the barriers identified and meet the expectations created.

After the presentations from invited speakers and the project representatives, a panel discussion chaired by OPEN DEI was held, whose main conclusions are summarized here below:

- The Smart Grids value chain will be probably the first to implement a data sharing architecture.

- In order to achieve a common European Data Space, all data sharing architectures currently under research should have a common baseline, a common language and share the same technical standards, so that in the future they can all be interconnected.
- In addition to demonstrating whether the analysed architecture works, the Pilots must contribute to promote trust and interest in the product by end-users and must be kept in operation beyond the project lifetime to be really useful and effective.

Figure 68: PLATOON presentation-Hub session on “Energy Data Spaces” (ENLIT Europe 2021)

- PLATOON Keynote and Session at the Belgrade Big Data Analytics Summer School ³⁸

3.9.4 Workshops and meetings with stakeholders at national and regional level

The Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) has organized several workshops at regional level with energy stakeholders, aimed to disseminate the PLATOON Open Calls and promote participation from the industrial ecosystem, with a special focus on SMEs and start-ups.

PLATOON 1st Open Call Webinar with Basque companies (January 27th, 2021)

The Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) organized a webinar together with Tecnalía on January 27th to disseminate the Open Call among Basque companies (mainly SMEs & startups). The event brought together representatives from twenty-one companies and other organisations interested in developing technological solutions to foster digitalisation in the energy sector, specifically in the field of renewable generation, smart grids and energy efficiency.

At the meeting, held online on 27 January, talks were given by the Basque Energy Cluster Managing Director, José Ignacio Hormaeche (PLATOON Industrial Dissemination Lead), and Erik Maqueda (PLATOON Tech. Coordinator; Tecnalía). They gave a general overview of the

³⁸ https://project-lambda.org/sites/default/files/2021-06/BDA_2021_Agenda_FINAL.pdf

project and the open call process to be conducted, focusing on the features of this first call, running from 4 January to 4 March 2021.

The webinar was disseminated on CEPV website³⁹ and social networks⁴⁰.

Figure 69: PLATOON 1st Open Call Webinar dissemination on CEPV website

Figure 70: PLATOON 1st Open Call Webinar dissemination on CEPV social networks

³⁹ <http://www.clusterenergia.com/innovation/cluster-energia-y-tecnalia-presentan-convocatoria-abierta-proyecto-h2020-platoon-a-un-conjunto-pymes-y-start-ups-vascas-3>

⁴⁰ https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/

PLATOON 2nd Open Call Webinar with Basque companies (November 5th, 2021)

The Basque Energy Cluster (CEPV) organized a webinar together with Tecnalia on November 5th to disseminate the Open Call among Basque companies. The event brought together representatives from ten companies and entities.

At the meeting, held online on 5 November, talks were given by the Basque Energy Cluster Project Manager, Begoña Molinete (PLATOON Industrial Dissemination team), and Erik Maqueda (PLATOON Tech. Coordinator; Tecnalia). They gave a general overview of the project and the open call process to be conducted, focusing on the features of the second call, running from 1 October to 1 December 2021.

The webinar was disseminated on CEPV website⁴¹ and social networks⁴².

Figure 71: PLATOON 2nd Open Call Webinar dissemination on CEPV website

3.10 Scientific Dissemination (TIB-SDM)

The methods developed in the PLATOON framework have been published in various scientific venues, including international journals, book chapters, and proceedings of international conferences and workshops. Moreover, the partners of PLATOON have organized scientific workshops and summer schools. The scientific contributions have been conducted during the period M13 and M24. However, it is important to highlight that they have also been included in the reviewed version of deliverable D9.3 resubmitted in M20.

3.10.1 Scientific Publications

Journal Articles

- Denis Sodin, Urban Rudez, Marko Mihelin, Miha Smolnikar, Andrej Čampa (2021) Advanced Edge-Cloud Computing Framework for Automated PMU-Based Fault Localization in Distribution Networks, Automated Diagnostics and Analytics for Smart

⁴¹ <http://www.clusterenergia.com/actividades-cluster-2/cluster-energia-y-tecnalia-presentan-2-convocatoria-abierta-proyecto-h2020-platoon-a-un-conjunto-pymes-y-start-ups-vascas>

⁴² https://twitter.com/Cluster_Energia/

Energy and Power Networks. Applied Sciences (MDPI Journal IF 2.679) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11073100>

Book Chapters

- Valentina Janev (2021). Semantic Intelligence in Big Data Applications, In S. Jain, S. Murugesan, Smart Connected World: Technologies and Applications Shaping the Future, Springer International Publishing, 71--89, ISBN: 978-3-030-76387-9, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-76387-9_4

Publications in Proceedings of International Conferences and Workshops

- Carsten Felix Draschner, Jens Lehmann, Hajira Jabeen (2021) DistSim – Scalable Distributed in-Memory Semantic Similarity Estimation for RDF, IEEE International Conference on Semantic Computing, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSC50631.2021.00062>
- Irlán Grangel-González, Maria-Esther Vidal (2021). Analyzing a Knowledge Graph of Industry 4.0 Standards, Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2021 (WWW '21 Companion), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442442.3453542>
- Valentina Janev, Maria-Esther Vidal, Kemele Endris, Dea Pujic (2021). Managing Knowledge in Energy Data Space, Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2021 (WWW '21 Companion), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3442442.3453541>
- Valentina Janev, Dea Pujic, Dušan Popadić, Maria-Esther Vidal, Kemele Endris (2021). Reuse of Semantic Models for Emerging Smart Grids Applications, 11th International Conference on Information Society Technology, Kopaonik, Serbia, <https://www.eventiotic.com/eventiotic/library/paper/652>
- Valentina Janev, Marko Batić, Nikola Tomašević (2021). Integrated Energy Value Chains – Overview of Challenges and Technologies, Proc. of the 3rd International Scientific-Professional Conference Circular and Bioeconomics – CIBEK 21, 58--72, isbn: 978-86-89691-21-4
- Farshad Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Carsten Draschner, Jens Lehmann, Hajira Jabeen (2021). Literal2Feature: An Automatic Scalable RDF Graph Feature Extractor, SEMANTiCS, September 2021, <https://2021-eu.semantics.cc/literal2feature-automatic-scalable-rdf-graph-feature-extractor>
- Farshad Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Carsten Draschner, Jens Lehmann, Hajira Jabeen. Semantic Web Analysis with Flavor of Microservices, LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School and Ph.D. Workshop 2021, <https://project-lambda.org/node/491>
- Carsten Draschner, Farshad Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Jens Lehmann, Hajira Jabeen. Semantic Analytics in the Palm of your Browser. LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School. Doctoral Workshop, 2021.
- Draschner, Carsten & Stadler, Claus & Bakhshandegan Moghaddam, Farshad & Lehmann, Jens & Jabeen, Hajira. DistRDF2ML - Scalable Distributed In-Memory Machine Learning Pipelines for RDF Knowledge Graphs. CIKM '21: Proceedings of the 30th ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management.

Publication under Evaluation

The following publication was submitted in July 2021 and is currently under evaluation:

- Valentina Janev, Maria-Esther Vidal, Kemele Endris, Dea Pujić. Responsible Data and Knowledge Management in Energy Data Ecosystems. Under Evaluation since August 2021.

Presentations in Conferences

- Erik Maqueda. Technological challenges in data sharing for energy applications. PLATOON - OPENDEI - Conference: Data sharing and governance for Energy applications. September 2021.
- Ainhoa Pujana and Jan Helsen. Data Analytics Tools and Hybrid Digital Twin for Wind Turbines. Wind Europe Electric City 2021 Copenhagen. November 2021.

3.10.2 Scientific Workshops and Summer Schools

The PLATOON partners have organized various scientific events in the period M13-M24.

Workshops in International Conferences:

In the context of the Web Conference 2021, the 3rd International Workshop on Transforming Big Data into Actionable Knowledge (BiDAW7) was organized by Prof. Dr. Maria-Esther Vidal (TIB). BiDAW was held online on April 16th, 2021.

Figure 72: 3rd International Workshop on Transforming Big Data into Actionable Knowledge (BiDAW7)

Two articles reporting the results of research activities conducted by PLATOON partners were presented. First, the paper entitled "Managing Knowledge in Energy Data Spaces" by Valentina Janev, Maria-Esther Vidal, Kemele Endris, and Dea Pujic was presented by Valentina Janev. Then, Irlan Grangel gave a talk on "Analyzing a Knowledge Graph of Industry 4.0 Standards", work conducted by Irlan Grangel and Maria-Esther Vidal. More than 25

participants attended BiDAW. The articles are published in the proceedings of ACM WWW (Companion Volume) 2021.

Summer Schools and Doctoral Consortium:

The LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School and Ph.D. Workshop was held on June 15th, 16th, and 17th. This event was co-organized by Dr. Valentina Janev, and Prof. Dr. Sören Auer (TIB) and Prof. Dr. Maria-Esther Vidal were part of the Steering Committee of the event. During the summer school, nine talks were given by partners of PLATOON. The topics of the event were:

- Big Data & Secure, Clean and Efficient Energy
- Challenges in Energy Management Solutions (Production, Transmission and Consumption)
- Renewable Energy Sources and Smart Energy Management

- Smart Grids Management
- Building Energy Management System
- Big Data & Analytical Services
- Forecasting Models
- Predictive Maintenance
- Energy Usage Optimization
- Semantic Technologies for Energy
- Semantic Models and Standards
- Knowledge Graphs in the Energy Domain
- Interoperability and European Data Spaces

The agenda of the Summer School is as follows:

Figure 73: Agenda of the LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School (Part 1)

Session 1: Tuesday, June 15, 10:15am-12:30pm		
10:00	Establishing connections (see instructions below)	
10:15	Welcome speech and introducing the Programme	Chair: Valentina Janev, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
10:30	Digital PLatform and analytical TOOlS for eNergy	Philippe Calvez, ENGIE, France
11:15	Break	
11:30	Scalable Reasoning in Knowledge Graphs: Theory, Practice and Use Cases of Modern Artificial Intelligence	Emanuel Sallinger, University of Oxford, UK; TU Wien, Austria
12:30	Lunch Break	
Session 2: Tuesday, June 15, 13:30pm-15:30pm		
13:30	Introducing the Programme	Chair: Diego Collarana, Fraunhofer IAIS, Germany
13:35	Financial Privacy with Knowledge Graphs	Luigi Bellomarini, Bank of Italy
13:55	IDS and GAIA-X: Sovereignty-preserving Data Exchange in Cloud Ecosystems	Sebastian Bader, Fraunhofer IAIS, Germany
14:25	Managing Knowledge in Energy Data Spaces	Valentina Janev; Maria-Esther Vidal Institute Mihajlo Pupin; German National Library of Science and Technology and L3S Research Center, Germany
14:50	INTERSTAT: a framework for Open Statistical Data Interoperability	Martino Maggio, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica SPA, Italy
15:20	Break	
Session 3: Tuesday, June 15, 15:30pm-16:30pm		
15:30	Introducing the Programme	Chair: Milena Jovašević-Stojanović, Vinča Nuclear Research Institute, Serbia
15:35	High resolution Urban Air Quality Monitoring: Hierarchical IoT Architecture and Edge AI Pipeline for Citizen Science	Saverio De Vito, Agenzia Nazionale Nuove Tecnologie Energia e Ambiente, Italy
16:00	Probabilistic empirical modelling of air pollution	Juš Kocijan, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
16:25	Q & A	
16:30	End of the Programme	

Figure 74: Agenda of the LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School (Part 2)

Session 4: Wednesday, June 16, 9:30am-12:30pm		
09:30	Establishing connections (see instructions below)	
09:45	Managing Knowledge in Energy Data Spaces – Serbian Pilot (Discussion)	Valentina Janev; Maria-Esther Vidal Institute Mihajlo Pupin; German National Library of Science and Technology and L3S Research Center, Germany
10:00	PLATOON Analytics Toolbox	Erik Maqueda Moro, Tecnalia, Spain
10:30	Edge computing in Energy Systems	Andrej Čampa, ComSensus, Slovenia
11:00	Break	
11:15	PLATOON Semantic Models	Sarra Ben Abbes, Lynda Temal, ENGIE, France
11:45	Semantic Data Lakes: Semantic-based Virtual Data Lakes for Data Science	Kemele Endris, Maria-Esther Vidal German National Library of Science and Technology and L3S Research Center, Germany
12:15	Lunch Break	
Session 5: Wednesday, June 16, 13:30pm-17:00pm		
13:30	Introducing SINERGY	Chair: Nikola Tomašević, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
13:50	Modern ICT/Automation Approaches for Smart Grids and Industrial Environments	Thomas Strasser, Austrian Institute of Technology
14:30	Reference architectures for Smart Grids	Friederich Kupzog, Austrian Institute of Technology
15:10	Break	
15:20	Temperature Sensing Optimization for Home Thermostat Retrofit	Federico Seri, National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland
16:00	Reduced-Order Models as Web Application for Energy Management: Barriers and Challenge	Luis M. Blanes, National University of Ireland, Galway, Ireland
16:40	End of the Programme	

Additionally, members of the PLATOON consortium, also actively participated in the PhD Workshop. Specifically, three PhD students who are part of the PLATOON project presented their work in the workshop. The agenda of the PhD workshop includes:

Figure 75: Agenda of the LAMBDA Big Data Analytics Summer School (Part 3)

Session 1: Thursday, June 17, 9:30am-12:30pm	
09:00	Establishing connections [see instructions below]
09:30	Welcome speech and introducing the Programme Chair: Sahar Vahdati, Institut für Angewandte Informatik, Germany
09:35	Keynote Damien Graux, INRIA Sophia Antipolis – Méditerranée, France
10:20	Semantic Web Analysis with Flavor of Micro-Services Farshad Bakshshandegan Moghaddam, Carsten Draschner, Jens Lehmann and Hajira Jabben University of Bonn, Germany
10:40	Semantic Analytics in the Palm of Your Browser Carsten Felix Draschner, Farshad Bakshshandegan Moghaddam, Jens Lehmann and Hajira Jabben University of Bonn, Germany
11:00	Break
11:20	Detecting Related Sustainable Development Indicators Through Text Ana Gjorgjević, Kostadin Mishev, Dimitar Trajanov and Ljupco Kocarev Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, North Macedonia
11:40	Experimental Evaluation of Scalable Infrastructure for Text to Speech Synthesis in Macedonian Language Kostadin Mishev, Ana Gjorgjević and Dimitar Trajanov Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, North Macedonia
12:00	A blockchain-based Platform for Keeping Logs of Citizens' Consents Marija Popović and Nikola Tomašević, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
12:20	Lunch Break
Session 2: Thursday, June 17, 13:25am-16:00pm	
13:25	Introducing the Programme Chair: Lazar Berbakov, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
13:30	Numerical Tools Developed to Predict the Combustion Behavior Inside a 20 kW Pellet Boiler João Pedro Silva, Senhorinha Teixeira and José Teixeira, University of Minho, Portugal
13:50	PMU-based Fault Localization in Distribution Networks Denis Sodin, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
14:10	Traveling-wave Event Detection and Localization on Power Cables Marko Hudomalj, Jožef Stefan Institute, Slovenia
14:30	Break
14:40	Machine Learning Based Wind Turbine Production Forecaster Dea Pujčić and Valentina Janev, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
15:00	The Cloud-based Control Platform for Multi-source Renewable Energy System Katarina Stanković, Marko Jelić and Marko Batić, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
15:20	Energy Efficiency Benchmarking for Smart Homes Marko Jelić, Dea Pujčić and Marko Batić, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
15:40	Coordination Platform for Handling Emergencies and Restoration of Power Grid Dušan Popadić and Marko Batić, Institute Mihajlo Pupin, Serbia
16:00	End of the Programme

3.10.3 Participation in Scientific Events

Dr. Valentia Janev (IMP) presented the data integration techniques developed in pilot 2a in the IEEE IAS/PELS/IES Austria Chapter Digital Transformation Technology Webinar (25.11.2021). The presentation was entitled “Integrated Energy Value Chains”, and Dr. Janev described the concept of Energy Data Ecosystem followed in the PLATOON project (described in Deliverable 2.4). She also illustrated how the reference architecture of an Energy Data Ecosystem has been applied to build the knowledge graph in pilot 2a. Additionally, Dr. Janev explained the analytical methods, implemented in pilot 2a, on top of the knowledge graph for forecasting load/demand and renewable energy sources.

Figure 76: IEEE IAS/PELS/IES Austria Chapter Digital Transformation Technology Webinar

3.11 Communication & Dissemination KPIs for 2021 (M13-M24)

Table 16: Comm & Diss KPIs for 2021 (M13-M24) - Reference Values & Actual Values

KPIs	REFERENCE VALUES	ACTUAL VALUES (M24)
Project Website	10,000 visits	> 12,800 visits
Leaflets, Posters	> 10 national / international events	24
Press Releases	> 8 press releases by end of the project	8 (32 overall translated PRs)
Social Media	1,000 followers on Twitter by end of the project 15,000 impressions	> 1,020 followers on Twitter > 1,750 followers on LinkedIn > ... impressions per month on average (M13-M24)
Meetings & Workshops	> 20 events	> 60

To conclude this chapter, the highlights of the WP9 KPIs achieved in the second year of the PLATOON project are briefly described below. Table 16 shows the KPIs that were set at the beginning of the PLATOON project as well as the actual values as per M24. Further below in Figure 77, the key highlights of the PLATOON comm & diss achievements for the period M1-M24 are shown.

In the course of the last two years, the PLATOON **Twitter** account acquired **over 1000 followers** while the PLATOON **LinkedIn** account gained **over 1700 followers**. As stated in the previous D9.3, these are outstanding results, given the fact that other H2020 energy project accounts that have existed for a longer period of time than PLATOON could only generate a smaller number of followers both on Twitter and LinkedIn. With the release of **8 PLATOON press releases**, another major KPI could be achieved during the second project year. A total of

32 different versions were released in 9 different European languages⁴³. **As per M24**, the PLATOON partners have visited **a total of 60 events**, both online and offline, of which 40 were visited by the TIB-KTT department. Just like during the previous year, all events were either energy- or digitalisation-related, or covered similar topics that were compatible with PLATOON such as sustainability, climate action, innovative technologies, among others.

To sum up, from a communication and dissemination perspective, the second PLATOON project year (M13-M24) proved to be just as fruitful as the previous year, and WP9 as a whole continues to produce excellent results and remains thus ahead of the schedule.

Figure 77: Highlights – PLATOON KPIs in 2020/21 (M1-M24)

4. Collaboration with BDVA/DAIRO

The PLATOON partners continued to further develop the already strong collaboration with BDVA/DAIRO during the second project year of PLATOON.

TIB-KTT has created a number of blog posts promoting the collaboration between PLATOON and BDVA/DAIRO. For instance, in M23, a blog post on the presentation of Alexandra Garatzogianni during the European Big Data Value Forum 2021 has been promoted on PLATOON's SoMe channels and published on the project website, as can be seen in Figure 78 and Figure 79 below.

⁴³ The languages were: English, German, French, Spanish, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Serbian, and Dutch.

Figure 78: PLATOON TW and LI posts on the European Big Data Value Forum 2021

Figure 79: Blog post on the PLATOON website addressing the participation in the European Big Data Value Forum 2021

Another blog post has been published in M15 on the PLATOON website concerning the presentation of the PLATOON project during the BDVA/DAIRO Activity Group Meeting No. 43 by the Coordinator of PLATOON.

Last but not least, the BDVA has promoted PLATOON’s 1st Open Call on its website⁴⁴, as indicated below.

Figure 80: BDVA promoted PLATOON and its 1st Open Call on their website

5. BRIDGE

As during PLATOON’s first project year, the PLATOON partners continued the close collaboration with BRIDGE, an initiative by the European Commission which unites Horizon 2020 Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands, and Digitalisation Projects to create a structured

⁴⁴ <https://www.big-data-value.eu/the-platoon-project-is-looking-for-bottom-up-projects-to-help-digitising-the-energy-sector/>

view of cross-cutting issues which are encountered in the demonstration projects and may constitute an obstacle to innovation. The Coordinator of PLATOON has regularly presented the project to the BRIDGE community. The communication team (TIB-KTT) regularly implement promotion actions and collaborate with the comm lead of BRIDGE.

Figure 81: Promotion of PLATOON’s 1st Open Call by BRIDGE on TW

Figure 82: Promotion of PLATOON’s 1st Open Call by BRIDGE on LI

Figure 83: Promotion of the BRIDGE General Assembly 2021 on PLATOON’s TW account

Figure 84: Promotion of the BRIDGE General Assembly 2021 on PLATOON’s LI account

Latest status:

PLATOON and TIB-KTT promoted BRIDGE's General Assembly in M15 via LI⁴⁵ and TW⁴⁶. BRIDGE promoted PLATOON's 1st Open Call on their LI⁴⁷ and TW accounts⁴⁸.

6. Assessing the Impact of the COVID-19 Outbreak

The PLATOON Consortium is updated as per all the measures of the EC with relation to the ongoing EU-funded projects and this topic is discussed regularly at the level of the Steering Committee, aiming to mitigate potential negative impacts for the project. Although there were some physical events (in correspondence with the continuously updating security measures with regards to the COVID 19 pandemic) where PLATOON has been presented, the vast majority of the events were online. TIB, as WPL9, facilitated this process in 2021 by offering online alternatives and will continue it in the next project year, e.g. by proposing to the partners the organisation of live sessions in which they can present the PLATOON project.

To counteract the COVID implications, the TIB-KTT team has been intensively active via social media and during online events and conferences, succeeding thus in implementing impactful outreach and project promotion across related and relevant stakeholders.

7. Conclusion & Future Outlook

In summary, the second project year (M13-M24) has been very fruitful and successful for WP9 and its Tasks.

The PLATOON project was able to further expand its established community and already high numbers of followers on both Twitter and LinkedIn, thus attracting more stakeholders from the energy sector and beyond. Just as during the previous project year, the WP9 Lead and WP9 Deputy worked increasingly online in order to adapt to the ongoing COVID19 situation. Therefore, most of the visited and organised events took place online and the online events remained the key for the expansion of the PLATOON Community.

Overall, despite the ongoing consequences from the ongoing COVID 19 pandemic, the TIB-KTT Division as well as FBA, CEPV and the TIB-SDM Division can report very large success for T9.2, T9.3, and T9.4. The PLATOON Partners are striving for a successful finalisation of the project in the third and last project year 2022 (M25-M36). It is expected that the PLATOON Community will grow even further and be up-to-date about all communication & dissemination activities, especially related to the results and outcomes of the PLATOON project.

⁴⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6772464579822788608>

⁴⁶ https://twitter.com/PLATOON_EU/status/1366688658821120000

⁴⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6757211368614633474/>

⁴⁸ https://twitter.com/BRIDGE_H2020/status/1351445101323706368